

Gender Equality
GE ACADEMY

D1.1

State-of-play map on GE in research capacity-building (SV)

June, 2019

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 824585.

Deliverable 1.1: State-of-play map on GE in research capacity-building

Deliverable ID & Full Title	Deliverable 1.1 – State-of-play map on GE in research capacity-building			
Date of Delivery	Contractual	M5	Actual	M6
Nature	Report			
Dissemination Level	P - Public			
Lead Partner	SV	Lead Authors:		Maria Sangiuliano & Marzia Cescon (SV)
Reviewer(s):	Lut Mergaert (YW), Elisabeth Kohler (CNRS)			

Version	Issue Date	Description	Contributor(s)
1.0	29/05/2019	First draft version	SV
2.0	31/05/2019	Second improved version including comments and inputs on good practices, taking business models into consideration, distinguishing between trainings, clarifying the rationale for factsheets' selection	Nathalie Wuiame and Lut Mergaert (YW); Elisabeth Kohler (CNRS); Vasiliki Madesi (VIL)
3.0	03/06/2019	Final chapter on concluding remarks added	SV
4.0	12/06/2019	Further proofreading and inputs from interviewed experts revised after their feedback	VIL

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List of abbreviations

Abbreviation	Full form
ERA	European Research Area
GEPs	Gender Equality Plans
NCPs	National Contact Points
RPOs	Research Performing Organizations
RFOs	Research Funding Organizations
MOOC	Massive Open Online Course
DOCC	Distributed Open Collaborative Course
ERAC	European Research Area and innovation Committee
GR	Trainings Gender in Research
GT	Gender Trainings

1. Introduction

1.1 Purpose, Scope and document structure

The present report is an output of Task 1.1 “Mapping state-of-play in terms of 'GE in research and innovation' capacity-building” of the project GE Academy. It also includes preliminary findings from Task 1.4 “Inventory and mapping of innovative training approaches and techniques”, which will be finalized later in M6.

The purpose of the report is to provide a mapping of the current status of capacity-building in the field of “Gender in research”. In particular, it provides a mapping of capacity building and training activities (both face to face, online and blended), on gender in research, comprising the 3 ERA priorities, being implemented in the 2009-2019 time span.

It also provides a mapping of trainings in gender issues more broadly meant.

Capacity building and trainings, both on Gender in research and on Gender in general, have been identified and classified according to different dimensions/variables.

The results reported in the present document will constitute inputs for a number of other project’s tasks.

In particular, in the frame of WP1, relevant results will be taken into account for conducting interviews with trainers, practitioners and institutions for Task 1.3 “Pooling experiences on promoting capacity-building on GE in research”, in order to investigate how to position the GE Academy “capacity building offer” on the “market” in the most effective way.

Also, task 1.5 “Defining priorities: formats, topics, target groups and key learning objectives” will design a capacity-building programme taking the mapping of existing initiatives and training techniques reported in this document into consideration.

Regarding WP2, “Content management”, gender training experts (both individuals and organizations) identified during the mapping will also be taken into account while selecting trainers for the network to be set up in Task 2.1 “Develop and mobilise network of topical and discipline experts”. Also Task 2.2, “Pooling topical knowledge on GE in research: inventory of key resources”, is linked with the results of the present report, especially with regards to Task 1.4, since its aim is to provide the most relevant and up-to-date key resources and training materials needed to feed the training design process. Indeed, the mapping carried out also points out relevant innovative training approaches and techniques as well as the formats, by also providing connected resources and materials.

During the mapping, all the different training formats that will be developed as components of the GE Academy project’s training offer, were explored. Namely, physical trainings, summer schools, interactive workshops, webinars, DOOCs and Train the Trainer sessions.

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Also, Task 6.1 “Building and managing a Pan European Gender Trainers’ Network” will rely on outcomes of the present mapping, particularly taking into account the experts identified and involved in this phase.

In the document, after the description of the methodology in Chapter 2, priority and more attention is given to analysing findings on capacity-building and trainings on “Gender in research”; indeed, Chapter 3 is dedicated to the analysis of results of the mapping related to Gender in Research Capacity Building, taking into account geographic coverage, timeframe, promoting institutions and beneficiaries, main topical areas and priorities covered, formats and durations and the intersectionality approach eventually adopted: main emerging trends are highlighted and commented.

Chapter 4 focuses on Gender Trainings more broadly meant, following a similar structure as Chapter 3, whereas Chapter 5 is about innovative training approaches and techniques that have been encountered and analysed through the mapping activity. The document also summarizes, in Chapter 6, inputs emerged during the interviews carried out with gender and gender training experts. Main key issues pointed out by the experts are spotlighted and some “lesson learnt” from the interviewees’ experience reported.

Chapter 7 focuses on a selection of Gender in Research trainings which are considered as potentially inspiring for the design of the Ge Academy Capacity Building program, in terms of innovative methodologies and formats.

Concluding remarks are presented in the final chapter.

The results of the mapping exercise have been organized and integrated in two spreadsheets/databases, one for the findings of “Gender in research” capacity building/trainings (Annex A to this report) and the other one for the results about “Gender” trainings (Annex B to this report), more broadly meant. The analysis carried out in the following chapters and paragraphs is strictly connected to the two spreadsheets. In the following paragraphs, continuous cross references are made to specific capacity building/trainings, made identifiable by row using the acronyms “GR” for the entries listed in the “gender in research” Annex A database, and “GT” for those included in the “gender training” Annex B database, combined with the entry’s assigned number.

The two spreadsheets/databases form an integral part of the deliverable (from now onwards referred to as “the map”).

2. Research Methodology for mapping the State of Play

Object of the mapping were trainings and capacity building activities on gender carried out in Europe and globally, in the last 10 years (2009-2019). In full scope for the research were those trainings and capacity building activities focused on Gender in Research, but for getting further input, the mapping exercise included also training activities on Gender Trainings more broadly meant.

Although the study adopted a systematic approach, it was designed giving priority to its design-oriented purposes and to draw an initial picture of gender in research training to be achieved in a relatively short timeframe (M2-M5 of the project). Some limitations should therefore be highlighted, in particular:

- the desk research was conducted in English (no researchers in national languages were contacted/employed). The only trainings included in other languages than English, are those which were indicated by project partners;
- the available documentation on trainings was often limited to a brief description and an agenda, resulting in difficulties in identifying relevant features and information;
- more attention and care were dedicated to capacity building/trainings on gender in research being the focus of the study;
- not all the stakeholders and experts contacted provided feedbacks and were available for an interview.

When conducting the mapping exercise, we took into consideration a **variety of dimensions** in order to adopt a comprehensive approach.

In details, the following dimensions were explored and tracked during the mapping and used for structuring the columns of the spreadsheets used for listing and storing collected entries:

- **main information** on: 1) Goals and Topic, 2) Specific Target, 3) Methodology, 4) Additional information such as the context (if the training takes place in a project framework or if it is institutionalized/it runs permanently), if/how learning needs assessment is performed, if/how the training/capacity building programme is subject to evaluation, if proof of impact is available, any other relevant and available features;
- **organizations** involved in the training/capacity building, considering in particular the promoting organization, the hosting organization and the implementing/delivering organization. In some case, two or three of them coincide;
- the **time frame** meant as both the duration of the training, and the period in which it was carried out. Only trainings implemented between 2009 and 2019 have been taken into consideration;
- the **countries** in which the training/capacity building has been implemented. This features mainly apply to face to face trainings, since online trainings are considered to be potentially implemented beyond national borders, the only limit being posed by language. For non-EU/EFTA countries, regional categories based on the UN classification of subregions are used;
- the main **priorities** covered by the capacity building/training, which include the 3 ERA priorities (Gender in Research content, Gender in decision making processes and bodies and Equality in

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Scientific careers) as well as other umbrella/overarching approaches such as structural change processes/methodologies and Gender Equality Plans. It is worth to specify that Gender Equality Plans represent policy tools within structural change processes: therefore, capacity building/trainings on structural change processes which focus on Gender Equality Plans have been indicated as having GEPs as main priority. Gender in Teaching has also been included to provide a more accurate description of trainings specifically targeting pedagogic and didactic aspects.

- for the Trainings on the Gender in Research Content as ERA priority, **topical areas** are defined as per the GE Academy concept¹: 1) Climate change, energy, environment (including food security, sustainable agriculture, maritime and water research, bioeconomy); 2) Medicine, health and wellbeing (including demographic change); 3) Information & communication technologies (ICT) and enabling and industrial technologies (including nanotechnologies, nano-materials, advanced manufacturing and processing, biotechnology); 4) Social & economic sciences and humanities (including inclusive, reflective, innovative societies as well as migration and secure societies issues); 5) Transport, mobility (including smart, green and integrated transport), urban and regional planning;
- **intersectionality** meant as other axis of discrimination/difference covered by the training (race, ethnicity, class, disability, LGBT, diversity, etc.). The fundamental importance of adopting an intersectional approach was also acknowledged by the *Madrid Declaration on Advancing Gender+ Training in Theory and Practice*², developed at the OPERA Conference on Gender+ Training in Madrid in February 2011;
- the **beneficiaries** of the training, in particular the main categories identified are the HR staff, middle and top management, academic staff and the administrative staff;
- the **trainer(s)**;
- **contacts** and any relevant **links** to the training;
- any stored **materials** and **resources** (i.e. agendas, programme descriptions, training materials, programmes' evaluation, etc.);
- any **innovative methodologies** used (relevant for T1.4, see chapter 5);
- the means to **promote** the training (when available, relevant for T1.3).

With the aim of drawing a cartography of the existing gender in research training landscape and with a design oriented approach, we referred to “good practices in gender training” in a broad and non-binding way: assessing or measuring compliance of the identified training activities with a pre-determined definition of good practices was out of the scope of this study.

Regarding the definition of good practices, according to what reported by UN Women³ there is currently no globally agreed definition of good practices in the field of gender equality. However, two key approaches can be identified.

¹ see GE Academy Grant Agreement n. 824585.

² QUING (2011) “Madrid Declaration on Advancing Gender+ Training in Theory and Practice, Complutense University, Madrid, February 3-4, 2011.” Available: http://www.quing.eu/files/madrid_declaration.pdf

³ Compendium of good practices in training for gender equality, UN Women Training Centre, April 2016;

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One approach is provided by the European Institute for Gender Equality (EIGE), which identifies the following criteria for good practices in training for gender equality: ‘effectiveness; impact; coherence with the existing gender policy framework; efficiency; sustainability; European added value; institutionalisation; reaching a large audience; evidence of positive results; and use of innovative methods’⁴.

The other approach derives from the QUING-OPERA and TARGET research projects, which identify good practices as “practices offering greater potentiality in terms of negotiation with commissioners, format-setting, applied methodologies, contents, evaluation or self-reflexivity”. In this report, our reflections were mostly oriented to considering potentials of collected practices rather than their impacts.

Anyway, a dedicated project’s WP (“WP3 Quality Standards”) is in parallel analysing the rich literature on the issue in order to compose the GE Academy set of quality standards that all formats will have to comply with. Therefore, what is named as ‘good practice’ in this report reflects those trainings which, based on the expertise of the authors, the project’s partners and the consulted experts, are considered to be inspiring good examples to start with the design of the GE Academy programme.

2.1 First step - Desk and keywords research

A two-step process was adopted for mapping capacity building and training activities and collecting the relevant information/data:

- desk and keywords research;
- second step - experts’/stakeholders’ involvement.

As part of the first step, an initial screen of Gender in research Capacity building in structural change and GEPs projects under FP7/H2020 was carried out using the CORDIS database. In order to conduct the screening activity, all the relevant structural change/GEPs projects were identified and listed. For each of them, the coordinator and/or supporting partners were contacted by e-mail and asked for providing any useful information regarding the capacity building and training actions carried out in the frame of the project. All the provided information and documents have been analysed and reported in the map. In case of no feedback received by the project coordinators, an ad hoc desk research was conducted. The same process was followed for projects identified through GenPORT and EUROGENDER.

The literature about standards already selected by the partner in charge of WP3 “Quality standards” (K&I) was also used as a source of information. Additional information about the relevant trainings identified via the literature on standards were then collected through a dedicated desk research.

In addition, inputs were asked to experts among the GE Academy partners: all partners were asked to download the spreadsheet, fill it with any relevant capacity building/training courses, and upload it in the dedicated folder created in GDrive.

⁴ European Institute for Gender Equality (EIGE), Mapping gender training in the European Union and Croatia – Synthesis report. Luxembourg: Publications Office of the European Union, 2013

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The desk research also included a **keywords research**, which also followed two phases. In order to conduct the keywords research, Google was used as search engine.

In the first phase a keywords research was carried out using the following search strings, all of them combined first with “training” and then with “capacity building”:

- gender (equality/inequality) in/and (scientific) research (content);
- gender (equality/inequality/women) in/and academia;
- gender (equality/inequality) in/and innovation;
- gender (equality/inequality/women) scientific careers;
- gender (equality/inequality/women/female representation) decision making processes (in research institutions/academia);
- gender (equality/inequality) recruitment (in research institutions/academia)
- sexual harassment (in academia)
- structural change;
- gender equality plans.

In total, 84 combinations of keywords were used during this first phase and 89 entries were found and added to the map. Only the first three results’ pages showed by the search engine were considered for each string/keywords combination, considering a decreasing relevance for the following ones.

During the first phase, a number of particularly relevant keywords combinations, in terms of results provided, were identified: “gender in research”, “gender in academia”, “gender in innovation”, “gender in scientific careers”, “gender in decision making process” and “gender equality plans”. The 6 mentioned relevant combinations were also used for a further keywords research combining all of them with “train the trainers”, “MOOC”, “DOCC”, “Knowledge transfer”, “learning”. In this second phase, other 30 combinations were explored, and 17 more entries identified and added to the mapping.

2.2 Second step - Experts’ involvement

The second step of the mapping exercise was intended to deepen the research, in case particularly interesting and innovative approaches or methodologies were detected and in case certain Member States or EU sub-regions appeared to be poorly/not covered.

Also, in the second step, contacts have been taken with stakeholders/trainers/experts already supporting GE Academy⁵.

The involvement of stakeholders/trainers/experts was mainly meant to:

- identify and highlight further good and promising practices on gender training/capacity building;
- achieve a fine-grained understanding of specific activities, methods/features that worked well and could be replicated in relation to given contexts;
- get insights on methods and formats that did not work in the experts’ experiences, within given contexts and conditions.

⁵ Experts and stakeholders were selected among those who provided a signed letter of support to the project to be part of the project’s community of stakeholders during the submission phase.

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In particular, the following stakeholders were contacted:

- All European Academies (ALLEA);
- European Women Rectors Associations (EWORA);
- European Platform of Women Scientists (EPWS);
- International Society for Gender Medicine (IGM);
- GenPORT.

An e-mail was sent asking for their contribution to identify good and promising practices of gender training/capacity building, especially with focus on gender in research/structural change, by providing via e-mail any useful links and documentation⁶.

Also, gender equality experts were contacted among those who expressed their interest to be trained and join the Pan European Gender Trainers' Network that will be established within the project (Annex 2 of the GA). They were proposed, at first, to provide links and documentation about trainings/capacity building initiatives they had run (or were still running) or they had been somehow involved or in touch with, that they would highlight as good or promising practices and/or as having a particularly innovative features. Secondly, they were asked for the availability for an interview (via concall) in order to investigate more in depth, the trainings/capacity building initiatives features mainly as concerns formats, used methodologies and evaluation methods.

14 experts were contacted, 7 replied providing links and materials, and 4 of them were interviewed.

The following experts were interviewed:

- Vilana Pilinkaite Sotirovic, from Lithuania, Centre for Equality Advancement, interviewed on the 21st March 2019;
- Katrina M. Uhly, from United States, Centre de Sociologie des Organisations de Sciences Po - Paris, interviewed on the 2nd of April 2019;
- Sheila Quinn, from Ireland, interviewed on the 5th of April 2019;
- Lucy Ferguson, from Spain, Graduate Institute of International and Development Studies, Switzerland, interviewed on the 9th of April 2019.

Also, the members of the GE Academy Advisory Board were involved in the phase through the same process proposed to the gender equality experts. 3 of them provided feedbacks and took part to an interview:

- Franz Wong, from the Netherlands, Royal Tropical Institute, interviewed on the 26th of March 2019;
- Kalypso Sepou, from Cyprus, Research Promotion Foundation, interviewed on the 29th of March 2019;
- Katrien Maes, from Belgium, LERU, interviewed on the 4th of April 2019.

During this phase, continued-refined desk research was also carried out together with direct exchange with trainers or owners of good/promising practices.

⁶ No specific definition of "good practice/promising practice in gender training" was provided to experts, therefore the information collected responds to what is perceived and considered as such by experts themselves.

2.3 Third step - Informed experts' interviews

An information sheet and a consent form were sent to the experts accepting to take part to the interview, in order to provide them with all information about the purpose of the study and the use of the information/data collected during the interview. The interviews were conducted through Skype and GoToMeeting. The interview was also recorded when the experts accepting it and provided the signed consent form.

The interviews were, in general, structured as follows:

- overview of expert's experience in gender training and gender in research in particular;
- identification of good or promising practices in gender training having innovative features, especially with a focus in gender in research;
- exploration of the best formats, methods and approaches to train and build capacity about gender issues in research;
- focus on
 - quality: what can be considered as minimum quality standards that gender training should comply with,
 - evaluation: how can gender trainings be evaluated
 - innovation: what we can be considered as innovative in gender trainings
- expert's opinion on the use of blended versions of training and webinars;
- specificities of gender trainings when applied to research institutions.

In chapter 6, a summary of the inputs of the experts collected during the interviews is provided.

3. Gender in Research Capacity Building - Analysis of results

99 capacity building/trainings (hereinafter also called “entries”) were found in the category of *gender in research*⁷, the majority of them consisting of a single training/session.

It is worth to notice that the majority of the results, 60 entries, representing the 60% of the total, come from capacity building activities conducted in the frame of EU funded structural change projects (FP7 and SWAFS). Among the 60 entries, 34 (58%) derive both from the analysis of the literature on standards and from the keywords desk research. 12 trainings were identified by contacting the lead partners of past and ongoing structural change projects. The rest of the trainings were indicated by GE Academy partners, as well as of some members of the Advisory Board and other experts.

All the above-mentioned results create a complex and heterogeneous scenario, which is explored in the following paragraphs through *ad hoc* categories.

3.1 Geographic coverage and time frame

The country of the hosting organization, that is the country (or countries) where the capacity building/training took place, was taken into consideration, for face to face trainings only, given that e-learning trainings can at least potentially attract a global audience. In most cases this also reflects the nationality of the participants.

The geographical coverage of trainings carried out within structural change projects and targeting all consortium’s members was defined counting for the nationality of each one of the partners taking part to the capacity building activity: the rationale for this choice is the expected multiplier event that transnational trainings involving all partners within such EU funded projects typically have in each partner RPO/RFO.

As previously mentioned, the mapping timeframe concerns the last 10 years; therefore, it is possible to find trainings organized back in 2009 until those most recently organized in May 2019. It is worth to notice that a few trainings organized in the frame of structural change projects (i.e. TARGET and PLOTINA projects) are part of a more extensive programme of trainings that is still ongoing.

By dividing all the gender in research trainings identified into the two periods - 2009-2013 and 2014-2020 - it is interesting to notice how only 14 trainings have been carried out from 2009 to 2013, while the great majority (over 80) took place in the period between 2014 and 2020. This could be justified by the impact of the web-based component of the desk research, where less recent items get less visibility, but can also be related to high share of trainings from structural change projects.

⁷ Those trainings (Gender in Research by YW and the Edith Stein School from GenderSTE) which were part of a series of trainings where same or similar sessions were repeated in several countries, were counted as one in the overall analysis, while each one of their sessions were considered individually when counting for the geographical and priorities’ coverage;

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Figure 1. Global coverage of gender in research trainings

The figure above represents the global coverage of the gender in research capacity building/trainings identified in the mapping activity (Annex A), divided per country.

Europe alone counts 85 entries and will be analysed in depth through a specific representation.

Beyond Europe, the number of trainings held in Turkey (11) and Morocco (3) immediately stands out. This is due to the inclusion of these countries in different structural change or RRI projects (i.e. Turkish partners are part of PLOTINA and FESTA consortia, whereas a Moroccan partner can be found in TARGET).

Moving to East, two trainings covers Australia and are organized by the University of Western Australia (GR2) and another one is carried out in Kuala Lumpur in Malaysia (GR7).

One training addresses Western Africa and is organized by the German Federal Ministry for Economic Cooperation and Development (BMZ) (GR4).

Concerning Europe, meant from a geographical and not political point of view, the situation appears to be denser and more varied, linked to an increasing activity from RPOs/RFOs in fostering gender equality

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in research. The biggest concentration of gender in research trainings is in Spain, Italy and Germany. This is the result of the high representations of the three countries in EU projects' consortia on structural change. Just as a note, the same countries have also been found in ERA Country Reports to be among the most active countries in terms of gender equality policies put in place by RFOs and RPOs⁸.

Figure 2. European coverage of gender in research trainings

⁸ ERA PROGRESS REPORT 2018, European Commission Directorate-General for Research and Innovation, Luxembourg: Publications Office of the European Union, 2019, p. 9

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Figure 3. European coverage of gender in research trainings

Spain resulted to be the country with the highest number of trainings, indeed Spanish partners are involved in the majority of structural change projects' consortia (GENDERACTION, EGERA, PLOTINA, TARGET, R&I PEERS, TRIGGER, LIBRA, and GENDER-NET). The case of Italy is quite similar, since Italian partners are members in a relevant number of projects' consortia.

In addition, Germany is also highly represented in the map due to the number of trainings from the BALTIC GENDER project, which is currently organizing different capacity buildings activities. In general, the diagram of gender in research training distribution in Europe can be seen as a mirror of individual single countries' level of involvement in EU funded projects on structural change.

Belgium, France and The Netherlands follow the first three countries in the ranking, as shown in the above diagrams. Austria, Norway, and UK have also hosted a relevant number of trainings, and Scandinavian countries plus Czech Republic and Portugal also appear to be relatively well covered, while **the amount of gender trainings to be found in the map tends to decrease in the Central and Eastern part of Europe**. According to our map, the GE Academy offer should be disseminated and delivered taking into account the unbalances shown on the map.

3.2 Promoting institutions, beneficiaries, resources

As anticipated, promoting, hosting and implementing organizations have been tracked in every capacity building/training of the map. Promoting institutions were divided further in:

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- Project consortium⁹, when related to trainings organized by the whole consortium;
- Research funding organizations (RFOs);
- Research performing organizations (RPOs);
- Other Public bodies different from Universities and RFOs (i.e. Ministries);
- NGOs;
- International organizations or networks;
- Private companies.

The figure below shows the distribution of the above listed categories among the retrieved trainings.

Figure 4. Type of promoting organization

As expected, it is immediately evident that the grand majority (71%) of the trainings were promoted by RPOs both in the frame of structural change project consortia and as individual promoters. In most cases RPOs are universities. The remaining 29% of the capacity building/trainings are mostly promoted by project consortia as a whole or by RFOs, as individual promoters or, again, as members of a consortium. A few trainings (especially those organized in the frame of structural change projects) feature both RPOs and RFOs as promoters.

⁹ It is important to highlight that in most cases consortia of structural change projects are formed by RPOs and RFOs.

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Indeed, as mentioned by Katrien Maes¹⁰ (Deputy Secretary-General of LERU) during the interview and reported in a LERU's (League of European Research Universities) paper¹¹, universities are using different approaches to overcome the problem of the lack of women in high-level positions and delivering trainings appears to be one way to raise the awareness and mitigate against implicit bias as well as to build the internal capacities to trigger change.

A residual amount of capacity building/trainings are promoted by private companies (2%), other public bodies (2%), NGOs (3%), International organizations/networks (1%), therefore covering just a little portion of the gender in research trainings supply. Public bodies tend to mainly cover the role of hosting organizations.

The analysis of promoting organizations leads to some considerations regarding the **resources** with which the trainings are offered.

At first, it is important to highlight that on the basis of the collected and available information, only three of the capacity building/trainings on gender in research identified were offered against the payment of a fee to participants:

- the summer school organized by The Committee for Gender Balance in Research (KIF) in Norway (GR56), which had a price per person of 6500 NOK (about 665 euro), covering return flights, transfers, room and board for the entire week, as well as an excursion;
- the EUGIM Elenora d'Alborea Summer School 2011 on Gender Medicine, promoted by the EUGIM project (European curriculum in Gender Medicine) and hosted by the University of Sassari. The fee was of 350 euro in this case;
- the course on Gender & Research Methodologies promoted by the Netherlands Research School of Gender (NOG) and the Radboud University (GR83). The course was free for registered NOG members, PhD students from participating faculties and members of the Gender & Diversity PhD seminar. For the others the fee was of 200 euro included two full days of lectures/discussion, feedback on assignments, a certificate and coffee/tea during breaks.

In the majority of cases it appears how trainings on gender in research is made possible by EU fund. This is the case of those activities carried out in the frame of structural change projects, which as mentioned represent the majority of the identified offer, and also of a series of trainings funded by other EU projects other than structural change ones, funded within FP7 SiS, Erasmus+ (GR 66, GR41, GR43, GR69, GR99). Indeed, the entire package of 73 Gender as a mark of excellence trainings delivered by Yellow Window between 2009-2012 (GR 66) within a contract with the EC, adds to the amount of activities supported by EU resources. The 40 additional trainings of the same type (GR67) make a peculiar case, since some of them were delivered under EU-funded projects as Baltic Gender and Trigger, although the majority were commissioned individually by RPOs or RFOs.

¹⁰ see Chapter 5 and 6 for more inputs provided by Katrien Maes during the interview.

¹¹ Jadranka Gvozdanić, Katrien Maes, Tomas Brage, Karin Gilland-Lutz, Brigitte Mantilleri, Jane Norman and the LERU Thematic Group, Gender Implicit bias in academia: A challenge to the meritocratic principle and to women's careers –and what to do about it, LERU paper, 2018.

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As far as trainings not carried out in the frame of EU structural change projects are concerned, these were in most cases promoted by RPOs (universities). Out of 21 trainings promoted by universities, around the half was organized by inviting internal experts (academics) as trainers. The other half instead involved external experts, (either) academics of other universities and (or) other professionals (in a few cases belonging to private consultancy companies).

The remaining trainings can be categorized as follows:

- trainings funded by foundations (see GR11);
- trainings funded by public bodies other than universities (for instance Ministries, Public Institutes) and carried out by professionals/consultants (GR12, GR13, GR86, GR87, GR88);
- trainings organized and funded by Networks or Associations (GR98).

All together the emerging picture points to a limited size of the demand for ‘outsourced’ trainings where RPOs invest resources to directly pay for gender (in research) training services.

As far as **beneficiaries** are concerned, different categories were set, namely:

- Academic staff;
- Administrative staff;
- Middle and top-level managers;
- HR staff;
- All, when a training targets all the categories listed above;
- Others¹², when a training targets a different audience than the ones belonging to the listed categories (i.e. students and/or PhDs), or it targets a mix of beneficiaries, some included in the categories set and others not belonging to them (i.e. H2020 National Contact Points (NCPs), member of projects’ advisory board, and RFOs representatives), or the target is not specified.

It has to be taken into account that there might be an overlap between categories, in particular managers can both be part of administrative and academic staff, and HR staff can be also considered as a subcategory of administrative staff. Furthermore, the available documentation does not always describe target groups in a detailed way. The figure provided below is therefore only indicative.

¹² In case of capacity building/trainings reporting “others” among the beneficiaries, refer to the descriptions for detailed information (when available).

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Figure 5. Gender in research trainings: beneficiaries

As the diagram shows, **most of the trainings are addressed to academic staff**, which represents the 41% (41 trainings out of 99) of the different categories of beneficiaries.

This is strictly connected to the topic and the priorities covered by the trainings. Indeed, as it will be clarified in the next section, the majority of the capacity building/trainings identified addresses the ERA priority “Gender in Research Content”, where the beneficiaries are, as expected, researchers, therefore part of the academic staff (see GR8, GR14, GR15, GR 28, GR29, GR30, GR55, GR58, GR59, GR62, GR77, GR78, GR85, GR86, GR87, GR91, GR97).

A relevant share of the collected supply of gender in research trainings is also targeted to middle and top level managers (around the 22%): this is mainly the case of trainings organized within structural change projects that aim to develop GEPs in the institutions, by primarily training deans and leaders (see for instance GR18, GR34, GR39, GR43, GR46, GR70, GR94).

Also, the “others” category occupies a significant part of the results, as it represents 31% of the identified trainings. Examples of this beneficiaries are students.

Two examples of trainings targeting the ‘others’ subgroup are

- GR12, a training promoted by the National Institutes of Health (NIH) about “The Science of Sex & Gender in Human Health” targets researchers, clinicians, health care professionals, educators, and students;

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- GR17, GENDERACTION webinars promoted by the project consortium and targeting national representatives, including Higher Education and Research and Innovation ministries as well as H2020 NCPs representatives.

There are also a few trainings (3) that do not focus on a specific category but rather target all of them. These trainings are either webinars or part of large events (i.e. conferences with gender training sessions). In particular, the following trainings are targeted to all the beneficiaries' categories:

- GR45, consisting in the EGERA-STAGES co-event, about gender equality, organized by the EGERA Consortium and addressed to gender trainers, academic researchers, university managers, HR staff, diversity officers and other stakeholders involved in achieving structural change toward gender equality in academia;
- GR67, which refers to the one-day trainings carried out by Yellow Window in the frame of the programme "Gender in Research as a mark of excellence";
- GR71, concerning the Capacity building and awareness raising workshops carried out by the INTEGER Consortium and consisting in different types of workshops targeting various beneficiaries.

Finally, only a small portion of the trainings are specifically targeted to administrative and HR staff (7% and 2% respectively,).

3.3 Main priorities covered

During the capacity building/trainings screening, particular attention was given to the main priorities touched by trainings' contents. Initially, the focus was around the 3 ERA priorities which cover the issues of:

- Gender in Research Content;
- Equality in Scientific Careers (including trainings on career progression and work life balance);
- Gender in Decision Making processes and bodies.

However, after a first analysis of the existing trainings, decision was made to expand the categories' differentiation, by adding as additional priorities:

- Gender equality plans
- Gender in teaching, and
- Structural change process¹³.

The histogram below reports the priorities distribution among the identified trainings. It takes into considerations the overall number of sessions carried out in the frame of such capacity building/trainings included in the map, therefore it counts each session for those trainings part of series/programmes repeated in multiple locations¹⁴.

¹³ As already mentioned, capacity building/trainings on structural change processes which focus on Gender Equality Plans have been indicated as having GEPs as main priority.

¹⁴ Those capacity building/trainings where was not possible to identify the exact number of carried out sessions have been counted as one training.

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Figure 6. Gender in research trainings: main priority covered

As it is immediately visible, and as already mentioned in the previous paragraph, **the vast majority of trainings/sessions identified address the ERA priority “gender in research content”,** with 162 trainings¹⁵. They are mainly offered within EU funded projects and by universities.

In particular, this is the case for the already mentioned 73 trainings belonging to the EC programme *Gender in Research Toolkits and Training Activities* and were implemented by Yellow Window (GR 66) between 2009 and 2012. Beside the 73 mentioned trainings, around 40 additional sessions have been carried out since 2013 by Yellow Window in the frame of the programme *Gender in Research as a mark of excellence* (GR67), using the toolkit and the format implemented during the previous project and adapted to H2020.

Among the other worth to mention “Gender in research content” trainings we find the 8 webinars conducted in the frame of GENDERACTION (GR17) and the 3 workshops “gender in medicine”, carried out within the STAGES project (GR47).

¹⁵ It is necessary to point out that some training can be counted twice since included in more than one “programme” of training. This can be the case for instance of training carried out in GR67 and GR68.

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Trainings covering the “Gender in research content” priority can follow a cross-discipline approach or be declined following specific topical areas, most often they include a combination of the two, with an initial general session followed by a focus into one or two specific disciplines (i.e. GR15, GR55, GR86).

We have captured the distribution of topical areas among trainings on gender in research content and the **more frequently addressed disciplines are medicine and health**, which can be found in 15 trainings, and **transport and mobility**, which refers to the 12 trainings implemented by genderSTE network. In 22 trainings the topical area is described as ‘other’, these are the cases in which attribution of a specific category was uncertain due to lack of information. The 17 trainings with ‘all’ the topical areas regard cases of training packages that discuss all the listed areas, or tailored trainings adaptable to different areas of research.

Figure 7. Gender in research trainings: topical areas

Trainings carried out by Yellow Window in the frame of the *Gender in Research Toolkits and Training Activities* and *Research as a mark of excellence* programmes have not been included in the above diagram/count as each of them covered two or three disciplinary areas (chosen by the host organisation) through case study exercises¹⁶.

The second most covered priority is “Gender Equality Plans”. The specific topic of designing and implementing a GEP was addressed mainly within the framework of EU funded projects on structural change. These trainings are targeted to different type of beneficiaries, like administrative staff, partners institutions and organizations, middle and top-level managers, and universities’ equality officers. For instance, GR21, GR22, GR23 are three capacity building trainings organized in the framework of the TARGET project, oriented to project’s partners with the aim of learning how to develop and implement a GEP.

¹⁶ Gender in research, Toolkit and training activities, final report, European Commission, DG Research, 2012.

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Trainings about structural change process (15), instead, are those that present in a broader way the topic of gender equality within research organizations/institutions or that are organized on different sessions and deal with various topics that lead to structural change. In general, these trainings are offered by structural change projects to their target groups.

The ERA priority “equality in scientific careers” often appears to be articulated on one side in trainings directed to HR staff regarding fair recruitment, and on the other, in trainings dealing with the leaky pipeline and the advancement of women’s careers issues (see GR42 and GR72).

‘Gender in decision making processes and bodies’ is the less covered ERA priority in the identified trainings. This kind of trainings are almost always hosted and organized by universities and addressed to middle and top-level managers. They typically have a twofold goal: to raise awareness about statistics on women in scientific research careers, and to present good practices and strategies to get more women into decision-making positions (GR7, GR20, GR33).

Some of the trainings cover all the above-mentioned priorities. This is the case for instance of the *GenderSTE* trainings delivered as part of the Edith Stein programme (GR6), as well as the Gender training sessions developed under the GEECCO project (GR68).

Under the section ‘other’ a miscellanea of trainings was included on different topics (i.e. dissemination in gender in research, gender sensitive language in administrative documents). Finally, there are a few trainings regarding the issue of gender in teaching both directed to current and future academic staff members with teaching responsibilities. This issue is also part of different projects’ work packages, as TRIGGER, BALTIC GENDER, and Gender SensED (see GR35, GR53, GR69, GR75).

Overall, as elements to be considered in the GE Academy programming phase, we can definitely mention the good representation of the Gender in Research content priority, with an uneven coverage of topical areas (main coverage of Health studies and medicine). Furthermore, we would emphasize the low number of trainings offered to tackle the ERA priority on women in decision making.

3.4 Formats and duration

Capacity building/trainings on gender in research present different formats and duration. Formats were categorized as follows:

- webinars;
- other online courses, MOOCs, and DOCCs;
- introductory trainings (on-site);
- workshops;
- blended;
- summer school.

The following typologies to distinguish distance-based/online trainings were used:

- webinars, which are interactive, usually lead by one unique teacher or organization, and usually do not take more than 2 hours;

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- online courses, often divided in more than one module and lead by different experts and organizations;
- MOOCs, or “Massive Open Online Courses” usually conducted by one or two trainers and oriented to a big number of students who receive access to all the course materials.

Even though DOCCs, so called “Distributed Open Collaborative Course” represent an experimental feminist alternative to MOOCs closer to the connectivist MOOCs model, and they provide a source of inspiration for the GE Academy e-learning component, we did not include them in the mapping exercise and the annexed databases: they are, in fact, curricular courses targeting University undergraduate students mostly, more than training/capacity building activities. Still, we refer to DOCCs in Chapter 5 about Innovative Methodologies and included a dedicated factsheet in Chapter 7¹⁷.

As far as the distinction between workshops and introductory training is concerned, the two were distinguished based on some features: specifically, the duration of the training itself and more or less in-depth approach into the addressed issues:

- Introductory trainings usually last 1 day and serve as basic knowledge-transfer.
- Workshops are usually events of 2 to 5 days and they are structured with different speakers/trainers to go more in-depth with an issue.

The distribution of formats for the collected gender in research training is well illustrated in the pie chart below.

Figure 8. Distribution of trainings' format

It is evident how the **two most used formats are introductory trainings and workshops**, that together form the 79% of the entire gender in research training supply which fell under our radar.

¹⁷ GE Academy Grant Agreement n. 824585, part B, p.10.

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The relationship between trainings' format and duration that we could observe in our findings, is illustrated in the table below.

FORMAT	DURATION	NUMBER OF IDENTIFIED TRAININGS
Summer School	2 to 5 days	3
Blended	>1 week	3
Webinar	1h – half day	10
Other online courses	1h – half day	2
MOOCs	>1 week	1
Workshop	1h – half day	6
	1 day	9
	2 to 5 days	23
	>1 week	1
Introductory training courses	1h – half day	19
	1 day	27
	2 to 5 days	2

Table 1. Relationship between format and duration of trainings

For what regards online courses, the duration is often not specified (GR11, GR12, GR25). This is due to the fact that they do not always have strict timelines, but only an approximate period necessary to complete the course is set.

The majority of workshops last between two and five days, most frequently 2 days.

Almost all (18 out of 23) of the workshops with a duration between 2-5 days were carried out in the frame of Structural Change Projects: this is most likely due to greater availability of (EU) resources to organize the activities from the side of promoting organizations and time to be dedicated to participate to gender training activities from the side of attendees.

Twenty-seven introductory trainings are organized along one day, although a relevant share of other (19) trainings from the same typology many have a shorter duration, lasting between 1 hour to half-day. This is typically the case for basic trainings aiming at presenting the issue of gender in research through a first overview or being used as opening lectures for more in-depth courses. An example of this is represented by the training titled “Questioning Excellence: Study and training days on women's and men's careers in Academia” promoted by NCCR LIVES and the Equality Office of the University of Lausanne (GR5). This was organized in two half-days sessions and it is classified as introductory course since it is used as an opening presentation of a series of lectures planned along the academic year 2018-2019.

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On the other side, introductory trainings lasting 1 day often make use of practical toolkits and participatory methodologies beside presenting the basic concepts (GR13, GR68, GR76). Methodologies in use can include a combination of lectures, panel discussions, case studies and interactive exercises. For instance, the training session in gender in research of the Centre for Genomic Regulation (CRG) held in March 2010 relies on a combination of toolkit and case studies preceded by a general theoretical introduction of the topic (GR13). In addition, almost 56% of the one-day introductory trainings is organized in the framework of EU structural change projects, while the remaining are mainly promoted by RPOs.

It is worth to mention that a few trainings belonging to Structural Change Projects last more than a week and include a full training package dedicated to a specific sector of an institution, which followed a specific formative program during several months or even years. For instance, a four-years long plan was organized in the framework of STAGES project and hosted by the Radboud University of Nijmegen (GR39): it was built around 12 very short training sessions, for university deans/managers with limited time availability. This training was aimed at raising awareness about gender issues and specifically at increasing and supporting organizational learning on this topic.

Another example is the 6-months long training organized within the framework of FESTA project (GR49), oriented to the HR unit of the Italian organization FBK (Fondazione Bruno Kessler). The training was divided in 50 hours of classroom plus 4 individual interviews per person and it was designed to enhance participants' management skills, with a special focus on gender perspective.

3.5 Intersectionality

Another dimension explored during the mapping activity was “intersectionality”, to what extent gender is understood as interlocked with other axis of discrimination/difference (race, ethnicity, class, disability, sexual orientation, age, etc.).

According to the limited available information, just a few capacity building/trainings adopted an intersectional approach. This was the case of the Capacity building workshop provided by the Edith Stein Educational Programme (GR6), which in its modules introduces the concept of intersectionality¹⁸, but also of the 4-week MOOC “Embracing Diversity - T.I.M.E. Edition” (GR9) promoted by the D-STEM project, which focuses on possible practical solutions to adopt in order to promote the inclusion of women and LGBT in academic environment. Also, the training-sessions promoted by Kilden genderresearch.no “What is the gender dimension in research?” (GR55) offer an introduction about how sex/gender interacts with other dimensions (such as social class, age, geographical location, ethnicity, etc).

Even if it might be the case that an intersectional approach is present also whereas not explicitly mentioned/emphasized in presentation materials of the training activities, still our findings highlight a predominantly binary approach to gender inequality and a very partial integration of intersectionality in gender in research trainings.

¹⁸ See the dossier Advancing Gender in Research, Innovation & Sustainable Development, of the COST network genderSTE, edited by Inés Sánchez de Madariaga, 2016.

4. Gender Training

Even though the focus of the present study are the capacity building/trainings carried out on *gender in research*, a number of trainings dealing with gender issues more broadly were identified during the desk research. All the dimensions explored for the gender in research trainings were also explored for the gender trainings. While analysing gender trainings, particular attention was put in the identification of potential innovative features to be considered as inspiring for the GE Academy. The gender trainings are listed in the Database/spreadsheet at Annex B, which contains 110 entries.

The same methodology was applied as for the rest of the mapping activity, as explained in Chapter 2. The majority of trainings were found through the specific and detailed keywords research (see Chapter 2.1).

General gender trainings, when compared to gender in research ones, cover different priorities and are much more widespread globally, one of the main promoting organization in this field being the UN Women Training Centre.

Given these differences, in the next sections, the geographic coverage and the emerging trends of general gender trainings are going to be illustrated, together with the presence of innovative features of gender trainings which is also discussed in chapter 5.

4.1 Geographic coverage

The geographic coverage of gender trainings is better illustrated in the following graphic (where a division per sub-continental regions¹⁹ is considered).

Figure 9. General gender trainings: geographic coverage

Specifically, this figure shows the coverage of face to face trainings only, which are, in total, 83, but it does not include the online trainings identified, since they can be attended worldwide. As it is possible to see, in Italy, 10 trainings were found; the same number as concerns trainings in South-eastern Asia. In this last case, almost all the trainings are organized by United Nations agencies, like UNDP, the UN-Government Joint Programme on Gender Equality, and UN Women. Concerning Italy, instead, its significant position in the ranking is mainly due to the different trainings organized by ITC/ILO (5 out of 10), whose headquarters are in Turin. Then, a relevant number of trainings is hosted in The Netherlands and Austria, namely 8 and 7 trainings, and then 6 in Germany, Eastern Africa, and Western Asia.

4.2 Emerging trends: main priorities, formats, innovative methodologies

Beside the geographic coverage, another relevant dimension for classifying gender trainings is the priority they cover. Indeed, the trainings identified cover the following topics:

- gender and development;
- gender budgeting;
- gender equality/awareness;
- gender mainstreaming;

¹⁹ Sub-continental Regions are divided according to the clustering in use within the UN system.

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- sexual harassment/violence;
- ToT - training of trainers (about teaching methodologies/ feminist pedagogy);
- unconscious bias;
- women leadership/careers.

Gender mainstreaming results to be the most frequently addressed topic in gender trainings: there are 30 trainings out of 110, which are categorized under this priority. Another big portion of trainings is represented by the ones on gender equality issues or aiming at raising awareness about this issue (generally speaking), namely 26 trainings.

14 gender trainings are ToT (Training of Trainers), targeting gender trainers and investigate theories and practices in-depth, as well as training skills and methods, and how to better conduct a gender training. 10 trainings are about gender and development and 9 about women leadership/careers. 8 cover the topic of unconscious bias, whereas 7 the one of sexual harassment/violence. The last covered topic is the one about gender budgeting, which counts 5 trainings.

Another important feature to analyse about gender trainings is the format and duration. Of the 110 trainings found, 107 can be in the following categories:

- workshops, or in-depth trainings;
- introductory trainings (on-site);
- webinars;
- other online courses (with different modules and training materials);
- MOOCs (Massive Open Online Courses);
- blended (a combination of online and face-to-face trainings);
- summer school.

For three of the trainings identified, not enough information was available to gather the kind of format used.

Of the 107 entries, the 45% of them are workshops (48 out of 107), or “in depth” trainings, usually lasting from 2 to 5-days, which aim to present an issue in detail and often through direct involvement of participants (interactive methodologies). The 18% (19) of the trainings are still face to face but they can be classified as introductory trainings, due to their length (which is shorter compared to workshops) and their content as explained in the previous chapter. Indeed, introductory trainings last mostly from 1 hour to maximum one day, with some exception of two days trainings, but still having introductory features.

Having a look to the e-learning supply of trainings, the 15% are online courses (16 entries), from advanced e-learning packages aimed to provide a professional certification, to a series of videos on a specific issue (i.e. unconscious bias).

Right after this category, the 12% are blended trainings (13), that are a combination of online course and face-to-face training, usually lasting 5 days.

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Six MOOCs and four webinars were found, whereas only one summer school was included and it is the one carried out in the framework of the EGERA project (GT85: although organized in the framework of a structural change project, this Summer School from the Institute of Sociology, Jagiellonian University, Poland covered issues of quality of life studies from a gender perspective, thus is not possible to include it under gender in research topic).

The analysis of the formats leads to some considerations about the use of innovative methodologies. Within the map different categories of innovative methodologies were identified (as better explained in the next chapter). For instance, among gender trainings, the e-learning method (which includes online courses, webinars, and MOOCs) was reported in 25 entries. Likewise, gender in research trainings, also in general gender trainings participatory/interactive methodologies are often used: more precisely 24 entries have been classified under this category. Then, blended trainings form the 20% of the trainings having innovative features (as said above, there are 13 blended trainings). A small minority of gender trainings uses gamified approaches or theatre, respectively 2 trainings use a gamified approach and 3 theatre. For example, the training GT14 “Diversity, Gender, Equality” organized by CIDFF - Center for Information on Women's and Family Rights, during the two-days long workshop used different didactic materials, including questionnaires, videos and card games. This workshop is listed in the GET UP project's report²⁰. More information is provided in the next chapter about innovative approaches.

An example of training using theatre as innovative methodology is the training conducted in the framework of the USVreact project, named “Sexual violence at the University: recognize, accompany and rethinking response strategies” (GT25). This training was organized starting first with a body dynamics activity, and then continuing with activities such as problem solving, case studies, drama/theatre etc. Many of such activities started with a small group task and then proceed to a wider collective debate. Only after participants had discussed about the issues, the trainer provided theoretical background information. This can be seen as an interesting case, since it inverts the typical traditional training methodology, and for this reason it was chosen as a factsheet in this report (see factsheet n. 3).

All the above form an outline of the main trends that are currently used in gender trainings, providing the theoretical background necessary to investigate about gender trainings supply of the last decade.

²⁰ GET UP project (2018). Gender equality training: providers and offers. [online] Available at: http://www.getupproject.eu/wp-content/uploads/2018/01/Gender_equality_training_offer.pdf.

5. Innovative training approaches and techniques

The present chapter focuses on the innovative training approaches and techniques that have been encountered through the mapping activity.

The focus on the innovative approach of gender training/capacity building is part of Task 1.4 “Inventory and mapping of innovative training approaches and techniques”. Indeed, being aware that innovative techniques for face-to-face and online training are key factors for successful capacity building and transfer of gender knowledge, particular efforts have been put in the identification of capacity building/trainings having innovative feature, both through desk research and the interviews conducted with the experts.

The following methodologies and techniques have been identified as innovative and therefore taken into account during the mapping activity:

- e-learning, which refers to a course, program or degree conducted completely via electronic media, typically on the Internet (MOOCs, webinars and other formats);
- blended learning, which refers to an approach to education that combines online educational materials and opportunities for interaction with traditional place-based classroom methods;
- participatory/interactive approaches, which promote the active participation of trainees and ground learning into connecting knowledge and skills to be gained with their already existing experience. Participatory methodologies can also rely, although not necessarily, on the assumption that trainers and trainees have knowledge to share and can learn from each other;
- gamified approach, which is an educational approach based on the use of video game design or, more broadly, the use of gaming elements in learning environments (i.e. serious games);
- theatre learning, which uses interactive theatre/drama practices in the educational process;
- multimedia production, which consists in the use of multimedia products as an outcome of the training itself.

In addition to the above methodologies a particular attention has been dedicated to specific formats of gender trainings, namely the DOCCs, Distributed Open Collaborative Course and represent a feminist retooling of the MOOCs (Massive Online Open Courses), developed in the US by participants in FemTechNet. They constitute *“an alternative genre of a networked learning course that exemplifies feminist principles and pedagogical methods that support decentralized and collaborative forms of learning”*. Indeed, *“a DOCC is built on the understanding that expertise is distributed throughout networks, among participants situated in diverse institutional contexts, within diverse material, geographic, and national settings, and who embody and perform diverse identities”*²¹.

DOCCs are not included in the Map as they are curricular courses held at US Universities, therefore they do not respond to the training/capacity building definition we adopted for this mapping study. Still, since the initial design of the GE Academy Project we took into consideration their feminist pedagogic approach

²¹ <https://femtechnet.org/docc/>

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to online learning as an inspiring model for a more decentralized approach to e-learning programmes and we dedicate a specific Factsheet to DOCCs in this report (see section 7.5).

It is worth to highlight that not for every capacity building/training identified, information about innovative methods and/or techniques used were available, therefore trainings which have been attributed one of the above-mentioned categories are those whose descriptions emphasize the use of such methods or techniques only. Beyond the one carried out using the words combinations listed in the paragraph 2.1, an additional keywords research was conducted using the following additional strings:

- “Gender in research-blended training”
- “Gender in research- gamification”
- “Gender in research-theatre”
- “Gender in research -multimedia”
- “Gender blended training”
- “Gender training gamification”
- “Gender training theatre”
- “Gender training multimedia”

This keywords research did not provide with many results in terms of capacity building/trainings which use the mentioned innovative methodologies, it rather resulted in pointing at some useful literature that will be reported and commented below.

Generally speaking, out of 99 trainings on “gender in research”, 55 could not be classified as ‘innovative’. All the others (44 trainings), are mostly to be considered innovative due to the use of a participatory/interactive approach (22 trainings).

Beside participatory approaches, 9 capacity building/trainings on “gender in research” can be defined as innovative because of their e-learning format, which includes both webinars, online courses, and MOOCs. As concerns blended trainings, 3 were found and included in the map. The only three examples of trainings that use theatre practices are listed among general gender trainings. One TOT (training of trainers) and one training using SDD methodology (Structured Democratic Dialogue) have also been included (GR30 and GR36).

Only one capacity building/training on gender in research using gamified approach was identified (GR20), and one training delivering multimedia products created by participants as an outcome from the training itself is listed (GT 108).

In the following part of the chapter the most interesting and relevant trainings (both on gender in research and on gender more broadly) belonging to the above-mentioned categories regarding innovative methodologies will be reported and described.

5.1 E-learning and blended trainings

As concerns trainings using **e-learning** methods, they can either be webinars, MOOCs or online courses (composed by different modules), single training materials (i.e. video) and online discussions. The majority

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of e-learning are webinars and the most relevant ones are the ones conducted within two EU structural change projects: EQUAL-IST (GR1, Annex A) and GENDER ACTION (GR18, Annex A), which organized 5 and 8 webinars regarding the implementation of GEPs (Gender Equality Plans) and mainstreaming of gender in scientific research in H2020 NCPs respectively. These two projects organized webinars with the same structure: the duration varies from 50 minutes to maximum 1 hour and a half; in addition, they all start with keynote speeches and end with a Q&A session. EQUAL-IST webinars have also adjusted their approach as far as Q&A sessions are concerned as these have been scheduled after each presentation to make the webinar more interactive and prevent a decline in participants' attention. Nevertheless, they have different targets, EQUAL-IST addresses primarily partner RPOs, while GENDER ACTION's webinars are directed to national representatives, as members of the ERAC Standing Working Group on Gender in R&I, and to NCPs representatives.

Furthermore, 4 online courses composed of different modules were identified: they are all promoted by different organizations, even though 3 out of 4 are organized by research centres (both RPOs and RFOs), while only one was carried out within GENOVATE, an EU structural change project.

As far as MOOCs are concerned, a MOOC about gender in STEM disciplines was organized by the Milan Polytechnic University in the framework of D-STEM Erasmus + Project, in partnership with TUB (Technische Universität Berlin) and ULB (Université libre de Bruxelles). It lasted 4 weeks (see paragraph 7.1 for the factsheet with more information about this MOOC).

Online trainings offer a number of advantages, related, in particular, to the wider audience that can be reached. This works both at an individual level and at a collective/institutional one. If it allows to reduce costs and time for participants, at an institutional level permits to reach many more people than face-to-face training, at a lower cost.

Online trainings also support participation of those who might feel intimidated by attending n face-to-face trainings. However, in order to make online trainings effective, it is important to ensure the active engagement through materials and activities and prevent dropping out or discontinued attention.

Blended trainings combine distance learning with the traditional face to face methods. It can be defined as a "mixed learning" since brings together different methods, media and theories²².

The most interesting cases are those proposed by the UCM (Universidad Complutense Madrid) and by the University of Pisa. The training organized by UCM (GR8, Annex A) was targeted to professors who want to include gender in their research and teaching activities introduce a gender perspective is. It was organized in 5 face-to-face hours that serve as introductory lectures, and 15 hours online; at the end participants had to submit a four pages work following a provided template in which they have to apply a gender dimension to one of their research projects.

²² see Claudi Wiepcke, University of Education Swabian Gmuend, Ewald Mittelstaedt and Adreas Liening, Technische Universitaet Dortmund, Gemany, Blended Learning Approaches to Enhance Gender Mainstreaming, Asian Women 2008

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The blended training organized by the University of Pisa (GR77, Annex A), instead, is part of the TRIGGER structural change project. It targets administrative staff of the University for training them to use a gender-sensitive language in administrative documents. In addition, the course was aimed at fostering communication and institutional information (internal and external) to be gender-sensitive, to make a step further toward gender equality. It was organized in 8 units, 10 face-to-face hours - the first two and the last lesson - and 5 online hours, spread during 5 weeks.

According to the feedback received by interviewed experts regarding e-learning and blended trainings, webinars are not considered the best format for gender trainings, if not for basic introductory purposes to specific topics.

Vilana Pilinkaite Sotirovic explained that trainers face more difficulties in having feedbacks from participants using webinars, but they could be used as a way of introduction and/or follow up. Kalypto Sepou during the interview explained that in her opinion webinars can be a good mean for transferring gender expertise in research when used as an introduction to the topic to people who are not already familiar with it. She suggested that a webinar should last maximum 1-hour.

Katrina Uhly observed that during webinars people can get more easily distracted, but at the same time, webinars offer the advantage of being more flexible and easier to attend, since they can be accessed worldwide.

With concern to experts' inputs about blended trainings, Sheila Quinn considered that in her experience of training on gender equality not nearly enough use was made of what is possible technologically, and indeed some out-dated online modes are still being used in preference to newer and more innovative ones. Where full use is made of e-learning platforms, blended trainings represent a powerful tool.

Lucy Ferguson, while explaining her recent approach to alternative methods which use theatre, mime, music and image, stated that it is difficult at the moment to think about how to translate these “new” techniques in online trainings, but she does not exclude to do it in the future. Indeed, she claimed online trainings work very well, since they are also accessible and cheap. However, they need to be enhanced integrating feminist pedagogical theories.

In order to have a successful webinar, trainers should encourage more **reflection**, so structure the webinars more in terms of reflexivity²³ than in terms of conveying contents. A suggested method is to show a video to participants and after that to engage the audience with questions, not to ask for the “right” answer, but rather the one which is better reflecting their feelings/opinions. Lucy Ferguson suggested to use images as well in the frame of such exercises. The technique she proposed is one step forward, since it is not only participatory, but reflective. This helps, in her opinion, to get a continuous feedback from the participants throughout the training.

²³ Reflexivity vis-à-vis is also part of Prügl's ethical principles for gender training. Prügl, E. (2016). How to Wield Feminist Power. In M. Bustelo, L. Ferguson, & M. Forest (Eds.), *The Politics of Feminist Knowledge Transfer: Gender Training and Gender Expertise*. Abingdon and New York: Palgrave Macmillan. Also the UN Women Training Centre, in the Working Paper Series: *Quality in Training for Gender Equality* prepared by Lucy Ferguson (2017) mentions reflexivity as one of the the cross-cutting mechanisms for ensuring quality.

5.2 Participatory approach

Participatory learning is one of the four key principles, specifically for gender training, identified by the UN Women Training Centre together with the validation of personal experience, the encouragement of social justice, activism and accountability, and the development of critical thinking and open-mindedness. Indeed, “feminist classroom” is defined as a particular kind of learning space that is “collaborative, experiential, egalitarian, interactive, empowering, relational and affective”, having the aim of “supporting students to become sympathetic to the concerns of critical feminist pedagogy”²⁴.

In order to implement participatory learning in gender training there are some key aspects to take into consideration. One is for trainers to adopt a dual role: as facilitator and as learner²⁵. An example of method which adopts this concept is the “circulation of knowledge”²⁶, which involves participants in the construction of knowledge together with the trainer/facilitators, rather than the transfer of information from one side to the other²⁷.

The trainings that use participatory methodologies are all based on a user-centred approach, by tailoring on participants the development of the training’s content and duration. For instance, this can be done through the **selection of specific case studies that involve the actual work of attendees** (in case they are a group of colleagues or working in the same area). In addition, participatory trainings usually introduce practical toolkits and the organization of teamworks. An example of a typical participatory training is provided by the GENDER ACTION on-site training on monitoring and evaluation (GR19, Annex A). The half-day training was designed for participants responsible for program steering and commissioning of evaluations in the field of gender equality in higher education. Within this session, held at the Austrian Federal Ministry of Education, Science and Research, participants looked into recent trends of gender equality policies in the European Research Area and to the linkages between policy instruments, program logics and objectives. Then, the specific case of a “policy-field” being subject to an evaluation was discussed as opposed to a single program, in order to create, at the end, an overview on the strengths and limitations of different assessment methods and impact models. Thus, this training involved both a theoretical part and an interactive one through the use of participants’ inputs and teamwork.

Another example of good practice in the field of participatory trainings are the two promoted by ESCWA (Economic and social commission for Western Asia) about “Mainstreaming a Gender Perspective in Research” and “Gender Statistics”, held respectively the 16th - 21st October 2014 and the 24th - 26th June 2015 (GT109, Annex B). Both these sessions were targeted to ESCWA Gender Focal Points and they were undertaken in response to internal capacity assessment survey. Practical examples were drawn from ESCWA’s own work, to make sure the training was as relevant as possible for participants. Used methodologies focused on interactive, participatory exercises, and they were selected to help the participants learn through discussion, dialogue, and critical reflection.

²⁴ Lucy Ferguson, Exploring privilege through feminist gender training, European Journal of Politics and Gender, 2019.

²⁵ L. Ferguson (2019), Gender Training, A Transformative Tool for Gender Equality, Palgrave Macmillan.

²⁶ It is a method adopted by Promundo and UNFPA.

²⁷ L. Ferguson (2019), Gender Training. A Transformative Tool for Gender Equality, Palgrave Macmillan.

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An important component of a participatory approach in gender training is the **validation of personal experience**, which means encouraging participants to share from their own personal and professional knowledge, even though the personal experience of participants can come into tension with feminist ideas, if, for example, participants have not personally experienced or witnessed gender discrimination²⁸. One of the points trainers work on when focusing on the personal experience is the “privilege”. Among the techniques used by trainers, worth to mention is the “privilege walk”²⁹, which is an experiential learning exercise encouraging participants in a deep and meaningful reflection on the multiple dimensions of privilege, while facilitating a discussion of intersectionality. The activity generates high levels of emotions, allowing in-depth discussions of the intersectional and multidimensional nature of privilege and discrimination.

As concerns the input provided by the experts, Vilana Pilinkaite Sotirovic explained that **interactive exercises** and **discussions** are always useful, in order to encourage the group to discuss critical questions and find the solution by themselves, while the trainer has the chance to collect participants’ arguments and to summarize them. Also, she highlighted that another useful technique is to leave participants time for **reflection** and practical exercises during the training session.

The importance of adopting interactive workshops was also raised by other experts, in particular, Kalypso Sepou highlighted that it is central to be as innovative and interactive as possible. Therefore, PowerPoint presentations and lectures are discouraged. Interactive workshops can be obtained by giving to the participants “something to work on”, for instance the evaluation of a proposal, or some hands-on examples. Focus groups, round tables, working groups and discussion are encouraged.

5.3 Theatre

One of the worth to mention identified gender trainings using theatre as innovative practice, is carried out in the frame of the NÓS project. The training was developed by Quarta Parede, a Portuguese Association of Performative Arts, in collaboration with the University of Beira Interior³⁰ (GT108 also reported in the factsheet n.4 in chapter 7), under the Active Citizenship Program funded by EEA Grants. Indeed, the *Empowerment Labs* carried out within the project represent an example of applied theatre practice used as a mean to transmit and produce gender equality awareness and knowledge as well as to develop critical thought and transversal soft skills.

The proposed model of intervention is rooted in methodologies like the Theatre of the Oppressed³¹, which is called “collective creation process” in which participants have even a major role than into the former method. It offers a reflective approach through the combination of biographical and dialogical dimensions

²⁸ Lucy Ferguson, Exploring privilege through feminist gender training, European Journal of Politics and Gender, 2019;

²⁹ The origins of the “privilege walk” can be traced back to Foss and Carpenter, drawing on McIntosh’s seminal article. Lucy Ferguson, Exploring privilege through feminist gender training, European Journal of Politics and Gender, 2019;

³⁰ the University of Beira Interior was the first Portuguese university to create in 2011 a gender equality plan;

³¹ The Theatre of the Oppressed was created in the 60s of last century by Boal (1975) who wanted to use theater as a political, social, ethical and aesthetic work tool. The aim of this artistic practice was to contribute to social change and dialogue with other areas and to work as a strategy of emancipation for the people involved;

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and the interaction of learners and their environment. Indeed, *“the individual is challenged to establish a critical relationship between the way he/she reads the world and becomes aware of his/her own weakness and opportunities”*³².

The project consisted in an initiative of non-formal education aimed at developing knowledge and transversal soft skills to address the problem of women unemployment and discrimination by encouraging critical reflection and social change through artistic intervention³³. The beneficiaries of the project were female students of the University of Beira Interior as well as unemployed women. Each “Lab” lasted 4 months with one session of 2 hours and half per week. In total 14 thematic and theatrical sessions with more 4 additional sessions of preparation of the final exercise were carried out.

The approach for this project was innovative because it was based on the collaboration of performance arts and social sciences focusing on the challenges experienced by young women who would (try to) enter the labour market in a near future and those who were unemployed for a certain period of time.

The Labs included non-formal activities and theatre workshops. Some examples of the themes Gender consciousness through applied theatre discussed in the sessions include: “Gender stereotypes”, “Power inequalities”, “Power and participation of women and men”, “Work-family balance”, “Future perspectives” and “From me to the world”. The themes were initially presented to the participants through the use of literary works (novels and poetry), newspaper articles and scientific papers. The same subjects were transformed into theatrical exercises and symbolic performances. With these resources and practices, critical reflection was promoted as well as the development of personal and thoughtful visions of the world among the participants. This approach also created the conditions for the final step of each lab which was the collective creation of a performance to be presented to the community³⁴.

According to the results of the Labs³⁵, the learning approach was very effective and appreciated by the participants especially because of the absence of coercion since the theatrical practice results from a collaborative work in which dialogue is horizontal and each participant can freely express him/herself.

However, the used approach also presented some constraints mainly connected to the discontinuity in participation from some of the attendees, most likely due to its long duration, and it is indeed difficult to envisage transferability of such a model in the framework of gender in research trainings where time constraints seem to feature most of the existing models and practices. Still, some of the specific workshops (see above) could inspire role playing exercises within GE Academy, although they would need to be adapted to a different audience. In the frame of this project some multimedia products were also produced, such as photos, videos and others. All the materials contributed to the reflexive process with

³² Catarina Sales Oliveira, Alcides A. Monteiro & Sílvia Pinto Ferreira, Gender consciousness through applied theatre, *European Journal for Research on the Education and Learning of Adults*, 2019;

³³ Catarina Sales de Oliveira, Universidade da Beira Interior and CIES-IUL, Empowerment labs: Gender equality, Employability and Theatre catalyzing social change, *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences* 161, 2014;

³⁴ Catarina Sales Oliveira, Alcides A. Monteiro & Sílvia Pinto Ferreira, Gender consciousness through applied theatre, *European Journal for Research on the Education and Learning of Adults*, 2019;

³⁵ the results of the Labs are reported in the papers already mentioned;

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participants and provided valuable input to the project's dissemination. This is the only training found having multimedia products as outputs.

Beyond the good practices presented above, there are other examples of how artistic practices and theatre in particular can be employed to stimulate awareness, understanding, and activism about barriers to women. For example, the under representation of women in technological fields has been the objective of a recent play called *iDream*, which represents an inspiring example of theatre for social change although not directly applied to trainings. It was not included in the annexed Database as it is not a training itself although it resulted in a learning opportunity for participants.

In the frame of the *iDream*³⁶ project the goal was to raise awareness and teach how to challenge, change, and overcome inequities in IT fields³⁷.

The play was built upon a research on qualitative field study of women working in the IT profession. It helped to communicate, in a drama fashion, research results on factors contributing to the under representation of women in the IT field. The characters, plot, and dialogue of the play came from research results.

The play is an example of *transformative learning*³⁸: indeed the audience taking part to the staged reading *iDream*, who were teenagers and adults dealing with them (teachers, parents, etc.) declared to have become (after the reading) aware that the IT field is an option also for women and underrepresented minorities having overcome internalized stereotypes³⁹

Theatre is also used to reflect on organizational culture, such as in trainings where participants perform 'skits', where other colleagues can intervene and stop the action and explore is something can be done differently (Cornwall, 2016). his method is found to be effective when used to work with patriarchy in the workplace, as part of 'gender' equality and 'diversity' training⁴⁰.

Katrien Maes during the interview mentioned a good practice consisting in an event organized by the University of Zurich in June 2018. It was a [LERU Gender Conference](#) on "*Implicit bias in academia: a challenge to the meritocratic principle and to women's careers – and what to do about it*". During the event a theatre group from the US, associated with the University of Michigan, performed a two hours interactive workshop on bias, going through several scenarios within the recruitment committee in

³⁶ <http://www.idreamtheplay.com/>

³⁷ Eileen Trauth, Karen Keifer-Boyd and Suzanne Trauth, *iDream: Addressing the Gender Imbalance in STEM through Research-Informed Theatre for Social Change*, The Journal of American Drama and Theatre, 2016.

³⁸ Transformational learning was theorized by Mezirov (2000) and consists in the "process of deep, constructive, and meaningful learning that goes beyond simple knowledge acquisition and supports critical ways in which learners consciously make meaning of their lives. It is the kind of learning that results in a fundamental change in our worldview as a consequence of shifting from mindless or unquestioning acceptance of available information to reflective and conscious learning experiences that bring about true emancipation."

https://link.springer.com/referenceworkentry/10.1007%2F978-1-4419-1428-6_373

³⁹ Eileen Trauth, Karen Keifer-Boyd and Suzanne Trauth, *iDream: Addressing the Gender Imbalance in STEM through Research-Informed Theatre for Social Change*, The Journal of American Drama and Theatre, 2016.

⁴⁰ Andrea Cornwall, *Towards a Pedagogy for the Powerful*, IDS Bulletin, Vol 47, n. 5 (2016) <https://bulletin.ids.ac.uk/idsbo/article/view/2801/ONLINE%20ARTICLE>

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universities. During the role plays, a facilitator interacted with the public, discussing the gendered roles and bias that occur in the process. The expert described the workshop as very powerful, since the workshop participants witnessed the effects of bias and group dynamics first-hand.

5.4 Gamified approach

Only a capacity building/training on gender in research was found adopting a gamification approach. It is the “Developing Female Leaders” training promoted by the University of Bath and implemented by Mosaic® (GR20). Mosaic® is a Serious Game that uses gender as a natural starting point to encourage leaders at any level to discuss and reflect on the meaning and practice of inclusive leadership⁴¹. The peculiar feature of the training is that it combines a brief presentation of research on gender gap in business schools with a Mosaic® facilitation, where participants are divided into groups of 5, each group having its own game set. They play 3 rounds simultaneously using 3 of the game’s pre-printed dilemmas selected to facilitate reflection on the main points of the previous presentation. After each round, each group is asked to share the highlights of its discussion of the selected dilemma and share their responses to different elements of the game. In the context of a competitive, yet entertaining game, Mosaic® appears to create a safe environment for imagining and practicing what can and should be done to constructively resolve inclusion dilemmas.

Also, two trainings on “Gender Equality” for UNESCO’s staff included in the “Gender training” map use the gamified approach. These two trainings are the “Diversity, Gender, Equality” course (GT14, Annex b), developed by CIDFF - Centre for Information on Women's and Family Rights, and the Gender Equality eLearning programme of UNESCO (GT49, Annex b). Both of them include a theoretical part, and additionally make use of gamified approaches as questionnaires, video, card games (first one) or as gender lenses, a gender scorecard and a gender quiz (second one). The “Diversity, Gender, Equality” training⁴² aimed at acquiring tools for reflection on the articulation between notions of gender, difference and equality, at identifying and decoding the stereotypes involved in the socialization of boys and girls and at identifying and analysing professional practices that promote or limit the construction of equality. The Gender Equality eLearning programme of UNESCO is mandatory to all UNESCO staff and it aims at making a link between gender equality and the work of UNESCO, by presenting concepts as UNESCO’s priorities in gender equality, key concepts of gender equality, gender mainstreaming, gender analysis, gender responsive budgeting, result based management, and advocating for gender equality.

Games represent powerful training instruments and educational experiences. They provide a safe space for interaction and learning; indeed, if from one side playing is an activity which is perceived as being “outside the ordinary life” and not serious, from the other side it helps on creating “working models of human interaction”, and “enable learners to acquire and apply new knowledge and skills”⁴³. Games

⁴¹ <https://ontheagenda.eu/products/inclusive-leadership-game/>

⁴² GET UP project (2018). Gender equality training: providers and offers. [online] Available at: http://www.getupproject.eu/wp-content/uploads/2018/01/Gender_equality_training_offer.pdf.

⁴³ George Simons, Gender and Gamification: international academic collaboration, EAIE, 2018 <https://www.eaie.org/blog/gender-gamification-international-academic-collaboration.html>

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engage player emotionally, therefore are especially useful for addressing sensitive topics, such as gender inequalities and discriminations.

A good example of game about gender issues is the one created by group of international students of the University of Bourgogne in Dijon, France, with the collaboration of George Simons International. The game⁴⁴ deals with gender and sexual identity and allows the players to get information, exchange views, explore differences and things in common and gain an experience of “mutual acceptance”.

5.5 Other innovative training techniques

Beyond the innovative methodologies already explored in the previous sections, in the present one other innovative techniques are highlighted.

An innovative approach, particularly interesting for facing resistances during the trainings is the presence of a **male co-facilitator** especially when the audience is composed by male and female participants. This is the approach adopted during the workshops promoted by the University of Western Australia and implemented by Jennifer de Vries (GR2). De Vries' work is underpinned by what she terms the ‘bifocal approach’: linking individual development and organisational change⁴⁵. The expert maintains a strong focus on building the capacity of individuals to understand gender processes and inequalities and develops their capacity to build and lead more gender equitable organisations. She also gives big consideration to the engagement with men and women at all levels of the organisation.

Another approach worth to highlight is the one adopted during The Dialogue on Innovative Higher Education Strategies (DIES), promoted by the German Federal Ministry for Economic Cooperation and Development (GR4), which adopts lectures and practical exercise for **empowerment/skills development**, like, for instance, presentation, public speaking techniques, proposal writing skills and mediation/negotiation strategies.

Also, the approach adopted in the training hosted by the Radboud University of Nijmegen and carried out in the frame of the STAGES project (GR39) results particularly interesting. Indeed, during a series of short training sessions addressed to deans, managers and researchers, the Group Model Building method was used: it consists of a facilitator supporting the group of participants in building a causal/systemic model on the dynamic changes regarding gender equality within the institution itself. From the first qualitative steps where a causal loop diagram is collectively built for the problems at stake, a more quantitative phase follows to elaborate a stock and flow diagram, which allows simulation of the consequences of possible *solutions*. Later, consequences of the existing policies were discussed⁴⁶.

⁴⁴ <https://diversophy.com/collections/special-themes/products/copy-of-usa-gender>

⁴⁵ <http://www.jendevries.com/gender-strategy>

⁴⁶ Berard C. Group model building using system dynamics: an analysis of methodological frameworks. *EJBRM* 2010;8(1):35–46.

6. Key issues and inputs from interviews

As reported in paragraph 2.2, 7 interviews were carried out in the frame of the mapping activities.

The grid of questions/topics touched during the interviews are briefly presented in paragraph 2.3 and in Annex C. Experts. It is worth mentioning that, beyond what is reported in the following paragraphs, inputs received by the experts, specifically referring to innovative methodologies have already been integrated in chapter 5.

6.1 Suggested (innovative) methods, formats and tools

Experts were asked to explain what in their opinion are the best methods when dealing with gender training and gender in research training in particular, and beside individual opinions, the shared theme was definitely “participation”.

As concerns the methods identified by the experts as being particularly suitable for training about gender issues, Vilana Pilinkaite Sotirovic mentioned the **3R method**⁴⁷, which she defined as “*a useful technique to let participants acknowledge by themselves the gender gap and issues*”. The expert explained that this method represents a good way to develop **ownership of the issue** by **letting participants complete small-scale simple research, identify problems and find solutions**. However, she stressed that this method is very expensive and time-consuming. Indeed, it requires to meet the same group at least 4 times, to provide participants with ‘homework’ and to analyse their feedback.

Kalypto Sepou mentioned the **Gender in Research toolkit** (GR66) as a good practice elaborated and implemented by Yellow Window also during a seminar she attended, providing case studies of research projects from different disciplines/topics to be used for hands on exercise where participants learn how to integrate gender into research content applying a given checklist and having the opportunity to compare their ideas with a given solution on that same case.

Katrina Uhly, recalling her experience in the ADVANCE program, mentioned some **effective ice breaking methods** used to favour an exchange among participants at the beginning of the trainings: TED’s talks, images of “wearing a headscarf”, games in which participants discuss about their first reactions when seeing pictures representing stereotypes, role plays.

Franz Wong pointed out that there is not a universal format adapt for gender training in general, but the best **design/format has to be customized on the context and content** of the training.

Katrien Maes referred to an innovative **method to facilitate training evaluation and feedback collection**, used by the European Research Council and the Royal Society, consisting in showing a **video** before the training evaluation, and making it mandatory in order to proceed to the assessment of proposals.

⁴⁷ According to GEIE, the 3R method (later 4R) involves surveying and analysing an activity in terms of gender equality, on the basis of Representation, Resources and Realia. The method was developed in the JämKom project on municipalities and gender equality, headed by Gertrud Åström under the aegis of the Swedish Association of Local Authorities in the late 1990s. It has been used mainly in various municipal activities.

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Sheila Quinn explained **one-off trainings are not the most efficient ones**. In order for the training to be more effective, it should be combined with the promotion of change within the institution's policies. In this case, it is also useful to identify, either before or during the training, a person who is willing to take responsibility to ensure **follow up measures** and to keep a record of the changes that may occur after the trainings.

Trainings organized in **more than one session** are more fruitful, especially when organized in a way to foresee a first face-to-face training, followed by another one after a certain period of time. This allows the trainer to propose an assignment to participants between to the two sessions and to collect feedback after the first one.

In general, it is **crucial that the trainer is involved together with the promoting institution since the beginning to customize and tailor the programme**. She pointed out that it is very useful when participants bring to the training some policies or examples of what they are working on, to be used during the training. Lucy Ferguson, in her article "Exploring privilege through feminist gender training", proposes a methodology being "able to get transformative processes in trainings scenarios". She stated that the use of words is no longer effective, that is why she is starting to **work less with words and more with emotions, movements, and mindfulness**, and therefore, to use methods like theatre, mime, music, and images within her trainings.

To summarize, concerning methods, formats and tools experts provided the following tips:

- 3R method for multiple sessions trainings (summer schools);
- participatory and interactive methods are preferable;
- time for reflection is suggested as well as the use of alternative methods like theatre, mime, music and image in order to work with emotions more than with words;
- training with more than one session is preferable for collecting feedback;
- preventive needs-assessments is recommended;
- Gender in Research Toolkit as a good practice.

6.2 Good practices of gender in research capacity building/training, training quality and evaluation

Franz Wong, member of the Advisory Board, stressed that a gender training can be considered as a good practice if/when it is integrating an **intersectional perspective**.

Katrien Maes mentioned a university (the University of Freiburg) as being a good practice in organizing events specifically on **gender in research contents**. In particular, the University of Freiburg set up a workshop in which Londa Schiebinger was invited for covering the role of mentor for researchers from different universities and investigating with them whether and how questions about how gender was/could be taken into account in their own research projects. According to the expert, it represented a participatory type of event, and this contributed a lot to its success, thanks also to the presence of the Dean.

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Katrien mentioned the work of Naomi Ellemers, from Utrecht University, professor in organizational psychology and active on gender issues. In her work, she explains how to **move people's opinion about gender from a negative threat to a positive challenge** through a training.

Concerning the topic of quality in gender training, it is important to point out that according to the UN Women Training Centre there is no consensus about what constitutes “quality” in gender training, and about “what kind of mechanisms might be put in place for guaranteeing quality in this field”⁴⁸. Many actors and stakeholders, including the Expert Group on Training for Gender Equality⁴⁹ (UN Women Training Centre 2015a) and the European Institute for Gender Equality⁵⁰ have raised and discussed the matter.

Particularly relevant is the contribution of the UN Women Training Centre which identified the following quality criteria specifically as regards gender trainers: grounded, situated knowledge and expertise; context-appropriate specialist knowledge, experience and skills; skilful management of power, resistances and hierarchies; skilled in feminist pedagogical practices; adopting an intersectional approach and analysis; and demonstrating a commitment to continuous learning, reflexivity and peer review⁵¹.

According to Kalypso Sepou, the **quality of the training mainly relies on the trainer**, even though the organizational aspects are also important (the location, the room, the material, etc.), especially materials should be of high quality.

Katrien Maes stated talking about quality standards that it is hard to measure the changes in people's opinions on gender equality, it is instead more feasible to look for correlations between the investment on trainings and changes in statistics on recruitment in a given institution, even though it might depend also on other variables. This comment points to the **importance of considering/framing gender training as a step within a broader process of change, to maximize its impact**.

Lucy Ferguson mentioned a paper produced by the UN WOMEN training centre “[Quality Assurance Tool for Training for Gender Equality](#)” released in 2018. The mentioned tools aim at facilitating the application of the Training Centre quality assurance criteria to training. At each stage of the training cycle, specific questions can guide the training assessment, planning, development, implementation, monitoring and evaluation to ensure these criteria are considered through the process.

⁴⁸ UN Women Training Centre. (2017). Working Paper Series: Quality in Training for Gender Equality. Prepared by Dr. Lucy Ferguson. Santo Domingo: UN Women Training Centre. Available at https://trainingcentre.unwomen.org/pluginfile.php/72/mod_data/content/40218/03%20Quality%20Assurance.pdf.

⁴⁹ UN Women Training Centre. (2015, September 16). Joint Statement from Expert Group Meeting on Training for Gender Equality. Santo Domingo: UN Women Training Centre. Available at <https://trainingcentre.unwomen.org/mod/data/view.php?id=6&rid=389>.

⁵⁰ European Institute for Gender Equality (EIGE). (2014). Quality Assurance Mechanisms for Gender Training in the European Union: Reflections from the Online Discussion. Vilnius: European Institute for Gender Equality. Available at <http://eige.europa.eu/sites/default/files/documents/MH0113604ENC.PDF>

⁵¹ see ref. n. 24

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As observed in the UN Women Training Centre's *Evaluation Tool* "while there are a variety of publications on the evaluations from a gender perspective of larger programmes and projects, there is very little found on gender training"⁵².

Tools used by trainers for the evaluation usually consist of **questionnaires**.

Both Kalypso Sepou and Katrien Maes mentioned the use of **feedback forms or surveys**, made of short questions, maximum two pages, in order to get participants' opinion about the organization, the trainer, the content, etc.

In order to receive positive evaluation, it is important to clearly defined **in advance** both the target group and the content of the training, as this helps to match the expectations people had before the training with what they received.

As far as evaluation is concerned, Sheila Quinn, referred to the importance of conducting a **pre-assessment** or needs assessment to grasp the familiarity of participants with gender equality policies as well as their expectations towards the training. This serves as a basis to conduct ex-post assessment which can account for the training's impact, at least in terms of achieved learnings and changes in self-perception from participants. If multiple sessions are foreseen and the training covers a relatively long period of time, change should be even more visible. On training evaluation, Lucy Ferguson referred to a working paper she produced for the UN Women Training Centre "[Gender-Transformative Evaluation of Training for Gender Equality](#)", which also provides an [evaluation tool](#). The paper's conceptual framework is grounded in the principles of **gender-transformative evaluation**. This concept is based on a feminist approach to evaluation and sees the evaluation process itself as a process of transformation. The expert argues that a feminist evaluation approach is required for feminist gender training⁵³. Lucy Ferguson also mentioned a [webinar](#) she conducted about transformative evaluation of training for gender equality. This implies that evaluation needs to be integrated into all stages of the training cycle and not left for the final stage and that it also needs to be built into the training process⁵⁴.

To summarize, inputs received by experts concerning the training evaluation are the following:

- questionnaires and feedback forms are the most common way for evaluating a training;
- also, pre-assessments and needs assessments are commonly used for measuring the participants' "gender" knowledge level, as well as for identifying what they want to achieve through the training;
- gender-transformative evaluation as a new concept which sees the evaluation as a process of transformation.

⁵² UN Women Training Centre. (2018). *Gender-Transformative Evaluation of Training for Gender Equality*. Santo Domingo: UN Women Training Centre.

⁵³ L. Ferguson (2019), *Gender Training, A Transformative Tool for Gender Equality*, Palgrave Macmillan.

⁵⁴ As also reported in her publication: L. Ferguson (2019), *Gender Training, A Transformative Tool for Gender Equality*, Palgrave Macmillan.

6.3 Other insights and tips

Interesting inputs concerning the approach to adopt in gender in research trainings were provided by Franz Wong. In his opinion, in particular, there is the need of a more radical approach in gender in research capacity building which further integrates **feminist epistemologies** in more explicit ways. The expert highlighted that gender trainings need to unpack and analyse theoretical underpinning of scientific research. Secondly, according to Wong, it is important to understand which are the mechanisms that reproduce gender bias. It is crucial for researchers (and trainers as well) to understand the limits of specific research methods and consequently to make informed choices about them: for example, there is a tendency to overestimate quantitative methodologies in socio-economic studies which can be helpful, but has often the limit of not bringing out the gender context.

Additionally, he pointed out the need for highlighting the interfaces and inter-relationships between the gendered nature of research organizations and the one of the researches they produce.

In general, experts pointed out that in order to organize a good training is firstly important to have clearly in mind which is the **target group**, in order to understand which is the starting knowledge about gender issues of the participants.

In particular, Kalypso Sepou suggested, it is important when organizing trainings, **grouping people having similar level of expertise and designing different modules** according to the participants' groups knowledge. In the case of the GE Academy capacity building offer, since the target group is represented by high-level education organizations, she advised to **group together universities with similar policies and gender action plans**. According to the expert it is preferable to exclude participants that do not fit in the target group instead of having an unbalanced audience.

Katrina Uhly pointed out that gender equality is not something people usually think about in their daily work/life, so it is crucial to show them how actually these issues apply in real **life**.

Katrien Maes highlighted that there is a lack of trainings and events about gender dimension in research content, also among many researchers, management and senior leadership. Therefore, in her opinion, there is a need to take action to raise awareness about this topic.

Another topic raised by some experts refers to **resistances**. Resistances are defined by Lucy Ferguson as “productive tensions that are required in order to move forward with a process of personal and institutional change towards gender equality”⁵⁵. She defines them not as something to be avoided, but rather as an essential part of contestation required for transformative change⁵⁶. Resistances can be distinguished between individual and institutional. They tend to be expressed in terms of general values,

⁵⁵ L. Ferguson (2019), *Gender Training, A Transformative Tool for Gender Equality*, Palgrave Macmillan.

⁵⁶ Ferguson, L, 2018, *Gender training: A transformative tool for gender equality*, Palgrave Pivot, Gender and Politics Series, Abingdon and New York, NY: Palgrave Macmillan

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rather than in relation to people's individual positions and interests⁵⁷. Resistances can be categorized, according to Lombardo and Mergaert's work, in three main forms: "denial of the need for gender change"⁵⁸, "trivialising gender equality" and "refusing to accept responsibility for solving the problem". Resistances can be also identified at different levels: explicit versus implicit, gender specific versus non-gender specific, etc.

When specifically talking about "Institutional resistances", Lut Mergaert, in a 2015 UN Women Training Centre Virtual Dialogue on Resistances⁵⁹, identified three key indicators:

1. The context of the training;
2. The immobility or unwillingness of an organisation to change;
3. The conditions and modalities of the training.

Referring to resistance encountered during trainings, Sheila Quinn observed how in her experience, she perceived most resistance from those professionals who considered that gender equality had either nothing to do with their work or was a marginal issue; this applies equally to both male and female participants. Ms. Quinn observed that while it is generally understood that gender mainstreaming brings together two sets of knowledge – knowledge on public policy making and public service delivery on the one hand, and knowledge on gender equality on the other, there is an intrinsic undervaluing of knowledge on gender equality; that there is a trivialisation of information relating to how gender impacts at the policy sectoral level. An important aspect of training on gender equality needs to be on the specifics of how gender equality relates to specific policy fields. In general, the best way to face **active resistances**, she suggested, is to let participants talk and allow the engagement with and reactions from other participants. She also stressed, like other experts, the crucial role played by trainers themselves in ensuring quality, stressing how **vision and passion** are needed when conducting engaging and impactful training activities.

It should be pointed out that in gender trainings, **flexibility** is required for dealing with resistances, tensions and conflicts⁶⁰.

⁵⁷ Lucy Ferguson, Exploring privilege through feminist gender training, *European Journal of Politics and Gender*, 2019.

⁵⁸ Lombardo, E., & Mergaert, L. (2016). Resistance in Gender Training and Mainstreaming Processes. In M. Bustelo, L. Ferguson, & M. Forest (Eds.), *The Politics of Feminist Knowledge Transfer: Gender Training and Gender Expertise* (pp. 43–61). Abingdon and New York: Palgrave Macmillan.

⁵⁹ UN Women Training Centre. (2015b, May 6–13). Virtual Dialogue on Resistances in Training for Gender Equality. Available at <https://trainingcentre.unwomen.org/mod/page/view.php?id=2119>.

⁶⁰ L. Ferguson (2019), *Gender Training, A Transformative Tool for Gender Equality*, Palgrave Macmillan.

7. Capacity Building on Gender in Research- Good Practices Factsheets

The present section aims at highlighting some of the more interesting good practices of gender in research capacity building/trainings and gender trainings that were encountered during the mapping activity, and which are considered as potentially inspiring for designing the GE Academy capacity building offer.

The criteria which was adopted in the selection of good practices to be included in the following factsheets is innovativeness: we pointed out at practices which present innovative features in terms of the used format and methodology in the training approach. Therefore, the selected ones are trainings not necessarily belonging to the “gender in research trainings” database (Annex A).

In particular, we present an example of innovative practice for each training format to be addressed when designing the GE Academy programme. As regards e-learning, MOOCs, and DOCCs, (respectively Factsheet n. 1 and 5) are highlighted as innovative formats.

As far as face to face trainings are concerned, some good practices about innovative methodologies adopted during the trainings are provided. These include innovative training techniques (Factsheets n. 2), the use of theatre and participatory approaches including self-reflection, group interaction, body dynamic activities (factsheets n. 3 and 4).

We also highlighted one good practice related to blended trainings (Factsheet n. 10).

Factsheet n. 8 is considered as a good practice due to the use of a serious game to foster gender equality in decision making processes and bodies, while the remaining factsheets highlight different features or methodologies considered as innovative (Factsheets n. 6-7-8-9).

7.1 Factsheet

Name of the training	Embracing diversity - T.I.M.E. Edition
Reference	Annex a, GR9
Promoting institution	D-STEM Project

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Implementing institution	Politecnico di Milano
Language of teaching	English
Objective of the training and main priority covered	<p>ERA priority: Equality in Scientific Careers</p> <p>Objective: This course is aimed at understanding what practical solutions are possible to adopt for promoting the inclusion of women and LGBT people in academic, social, and corporate environments, and why gender and sexual diversity drives innovation and generates new energy. This MOOC considers the effects of discouragement and self-exclusion on female talent in STEM subjects.</p>
Country and area of implementation	Worldwide (Online course)
Duration of the training	4 weeks
Period	From the 29th of October 2018 to the 23rd of January 2019
Beneficiaries	Students of POLIMI, TUB (Technische Universität Berlin) and ULB (Université libre de Bruxelles)
Format	e-learning - MOOC
Methodology used	Videos, self-evaluation quizzes, activities aimed at raising awareness on the topics proposed, real case studies, discussion forum, and good practices
Trainer(s)	Andrea Notarnicola

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Innovative features	MOOC
Relevance for GE Academy	<p>-Specific module of women in STEM and how to motivate girls in studying scientific subjects;</p> <p>-Innovative format;</p> <p>-the MOOC's beneficiaries are students which do not represent the GE Academy capacity building offer target. However, the MOOC was selected because it represents the only one training found to have such innovative format.</p>
Links to relevant resources	<p>Course home page (visible after free registration)</p> <p>Video of course presentation</p>

7.2 Factsheet

Name of the training	Tools for teaching with a gender perspective: challenges
Reference	GR53, Annex A
Promoting institution	UCM (Universidad Complutense Madrid)
Implementing institution	UCM (Universidad Complutense Madrid)
Language of teaching	Spanish

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<p>Objective and topic of the training and main priority covered</p>	<p>Priority: Gender in teaching</p> <p>Objective and topic: This course aim to provide teachers with the necessary tools to focus their teaching activity with a gender perspective, both respecting the content they transmit as well as educational and training strategies, the knowledge they produce and the methodology they use. The course serves to promote reflection and knowledge about the differences and inequalities between women and men, emphasizing the character of social construction of gender and the impact it has on the academic world. The topics covered during the training are: analysis of gender inequality in socialization; incorporation of the gender perspective in the knowledge that is imparted; visibility of women in science and history; incorporation of the gender perspective in the bibliography; participation in the classroom and teacher-student interaction; use of a non-sexist language; studies on women, feminists and gender in the academic field; and challenges to gender inequalities in the university.</p>
<p>Country and area of implementation</p>	<p>Spain</p>
<p>Duration of the training</p>	<p>28 hours</p>
<p>Period</p>	<p>28 and 30 of January, 1-4-6-8 February 2019</p>
<p>Beneficiaries</p>	<p>Academic staff, professors of UCM</p>
<p>Format</p>	<p>face-to-face workshop</p>
<p>Methodology used</p>	<p>The course is developed through a theoretical and practical methodology. The face-to-face sessions have an expository and fundamentally participatory methodology. The course starts from the level of knowledge of participants and it is based on the following methodological principles:</p>

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	<p>a) Self-reflection to allow participants to self-evaluate their teaching and research practice;</p> <p>b) Group interaction to facilitate and reinforce individual learning;</p> <p>c) Practical exercises/ test to incorporate the gender perspective in the teaching and research practice.</p>
Trainer(s)	Mónica Saiz Martínez
Innovative features	participatory/interactive methodologies
Relevance for GE Academy	Relevant topic and methodology for a training targeted to academic staff
Links to relevant resources	Course description (in Spanish)

7.3 Factsheet

Name of the training	Sexual violence at the University: recognize, accompany and rethinking response strategies
Reference	Annex B, GT25
Promoting institution	USVreact project Rovira i Vigili University
Implementing institution	Universitat Rovira i Virgila
Language of teaching	Spanish

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<p>Topic of the training and main priority covered</p>	<p>Priority: Sexual Harassment/violence</p> <p>Topic: The training focused on understanding how culture creates the conditions that make SV possible and enables it, and also on the necessity to dismantle these cultural dynamics.</p> <p>Session one, part one: how do different forms of sexual violence manifest in university settings?</p> <p>Session one, part two: understanding, framing and defining sexual violence</p> <p>Session two, part one: how do we react? Perceiving, listening, caring, accompanying and evaluating.</p> <p>Session two, part two: tools, services and strategies for a fair first response in university.</p>
<p>Country and area of implementation</p>	<p>Spain</p>
<p>Duration of the training</p>	<p>10 hours, distributed in two sessions (over 2 days)</p>
<p>Period</p>	<p>Between January and May 2017</p>
<p>Beneficiaries</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Administrative and management staff -Teaching and research staff -Students
<p>Format</p>	<p>face-to-face workshop</p>

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<p>Methodology used</p>	<p>The training was inspired by the principles of feminist pedagogy: starting from the self and encouraging self-reflection by emphasising the relationship between the content of the course and the lived experience of the participants. This approach is also based on collaboration as a way to facilitate a greater acquisition of knowledge and to promote the development of community in the university, or at the very least, a network of people that are aware of and sensitive to the dynamics of sexual violence.</p> <p>The course was divided into four blocks. Each one started (1 and 3) or ended (3 and 4) with a body dynamics activity, and then continued with activities such as problem solving, case studies, theatricalization, etc. Many of these activities started with a small group task and then proceeded to a wider collective debate. At the end of each debate some theoretical and practical reflections were presented to the group using PowerPoint slides. During the workshops, videos and other support materials were used, such as an interactive map of Catalonia that displayed available resources close to the university.</p>
<p>Trainer(s)</p>	<p>Ivana Soto and Sara Cagliero</p>
<p>Innovative features</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -body dynamic activities -self-experience cantered -interactive methodologies
<p>Relevance for GE Academy</p>	<p>This training, even if not focus on the topic of gender in research, gives an example of a different strategy of doing trainings. It starts from the personal experience of participants, then it introduces theoretic concepts, in order to make trainees 'experience' what they are learning</p>
<p>Links to relevant resources</p>	<p>Report of the trainings</p>

7.4 Factsheet

Name of the training	Empowerment Labs - NÓS project
Reference	Annex B, GT108
Promoting institution	Quarta Parede University of Beira Interior
Implementing institution	Quarta Parede University of Beira Interior
Language of teaching	Portuguese
Topic of the training and main priority covered	Priority: Gender Equality/Awareness The project consisted in an initiative of non-formal education aimed at developing knowledge and transversal soft skills to address the problem of women unemployment and discrimination by encouraging critical reflection and social change through artistic intervention. The Labs included non-formal activities and theatre workshops .
Country and area of implementation	Portugal
Duration of the training	4 months with one session of 2 hours and half per week
Period	December 2013-April 2014 (Lab1)

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Beneficiaries	Students of the University of Beira Interior and unemployed women
Format	Workshop
Methodology used	<p>The Empowerment Labs made use of an applied participatory laboratorial practice, in which theatre constituted the privileged pedagogical instrument. Each laboratory began with a presentation session followed by two gender equality awareness-raising sessions led by a sociologist and a psychologist. An additional gender equality session was organised after 8 weeks to reinforce the conceptual and theoretical background. Some examples of the themes discussed in the sessions include: “Gender stereotypes”, “Power inequalities”, “Power and participation of women and men”, “Work-family balance”, “Future perspectives” (Lab1) and “From me to the world” (Lab2). The model of intervention proposed for the Empowerment labs project is rooted in methodologies like the Theatre of the Oppressed. Based on this perspective and also in the dialogue pedagogic concept (Freire, 1972) the Nós project developed an approach called collective creation process in which the participants have a major role into the process compared with the Theatre of the Oppressed.</p> <p>A number of materials were produced in the frame of the Labs like photos, videos, trainer’s field diary, participants’ texts, evaluation instruments and materials produced in the sessions. All these materials represented vital methodological tools for the workshops as they contributed to the reflection process with the participants and also provided valuable input to the project’s dissemination instruments.</p>
Trainer(s)	Professors at UBI
Innovative features	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -use of non-formal educational activities and theatre workshops; -approach based on the collaboration of performance arts and social sciences; -dynamic soft skills training;

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	-production of multimedia outputs: photos, videos and other materials.
Relevance for GE Academy	Although this training is not focused on the topic of gender in research, it was interesting to highlight given its innovative and non-conventional approach to the gender equality issue.
Links to relevant resources	Report 1 Report 2

7.5 Factsheet

Name of the training	Feminism, Technology and American Culture
Reference	This course is not included in the map given that the topic is out of content. However, this factsheet wants to highlight this course methodology.
Promoting institution	FemTechNet
Implementing institution	approximately 15 institutions, among which University of California, San Diego, Bowling Green State University, and Pitzer College
Language of teaching	English
Topic of the training	The course offers students and faculty the opportunity to participate in collaborative university learning by taking advantage of various digital platforms, including the Sakai student portal at Pitzer, Facebook, Vimeo, and Google+ Hangouts. This course emphasizes key issues in Feminism and Technology within

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	the context of American culture, Globalization, and Media Studies. Students explore gender and technology through 11 themes including: TechnoFeminism, machine, body, archive, labour, difference, systems, place, race, sexualities, and transformation.
Country and area of implementation	online course
Duration and period of the training	Fall 2013
Beneficiaries	Students of the listed universities
Format	DOCC
Methodology used	<p>This course is one version of a “Distributed Open Collaborative Course” (DOCC) taught at approximately 15 institutions, organized collectively by FemTechNet. This course uses technology for interdisciplinary collaborative creation and peer-to-peer sharing while still valuing local issues and face-to-face connections. The course is built around a shared set of recorded dialogues with preeminent thinkers and artists.</p> <p>An Online Discussion Board is set, which represent the online equivalent of face-to-face group conversations in which participants share ideas and questions about the course materials, and assignments are posted.</p> <p>This course is designed to foster a genuinely collaborative, dialogic learning environment, where both participants and trainers are partners in active learning, and thus become jointly responsible for the process of learning. Students collaborated by writing responses, producing keyword videos, contributing to Wikipedia, and creating crafts representative of the 11 themes for further connection and conversation.</p>

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Trainer(s)	Lisa Cartwright and Elizabeth Losh (University of California); Alex Juhasz (Pitzer College); Dr. Radhika Gajjala (for BGSU)
Innovative features	-Course distribution; -involvement of a network of experts, -collaborative learning/ peer-to-peer sharing, -e-learning.
Relevance for GE Academy	Example of DOCC
Links to relevant resources	FemTechNet course presentation BGSU Course details

7.6 Factsheet

Name of the training	Navigating Women's Careers in Higher Education DIES (Dialogue on Innovative Higher Education Strategies) workshop
Reference	GR4, Annex A
Promoting institution	German Federal Ministry for Economic Cooperation and Development (BMZ)
Implementing institution	German Academic Exchange Service (DAAD); German Rector's Conference (HRK)

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Language of teaching	English
Objective and topic of the training and main priority covered	<p>Priority: ERA: Equality in Scientific Careers</p> <p>The Dialogue on Innovative Higher Education Strategies (DIES) aims to improve university management in countries of the Global South through exchange of expertise and good practices. In line with Goal 4 of the SDG Agenda, DIES Dialogue events stimulate Higher Education reforms for an equitable, high-quality education for all.</p> <p>Objectives:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Capturing and disseminating knowledge for women’s advancement in academia; -Building national, regional and international support networks, -Enhancing the delivery of mentoring for female academics and researchers, -Encouraging female academics and researchers to apply for research funding and scholarships; -Mapping out a strategy to further gender equity in Higher Education in West Africa; -Equipping female academics and researchers with skills for advancing their own careers. <p>Workshop themes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Breaking the glass ceiling; -Coping with cultural norms detrimental to women's careers; -Dealing with bullying in a HE working environment; -Lobbying for gender issues; -Entrepreneurial and innovative skills for women; -Women scientists in STEM.
Country and area of implementation	Accra, Ghana
Duration of the training	3 days

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Period	10-12 April 2019
Beneficiaries	Female decision-makers in higher education, university managers of middle and upper leadership level, established and emerging (minimum: Masters' degree level) female academics and researchers from institutes of higher education and research institutes in Ghana and West Africa.
Format	workshop/ in depth
Methodology used	Lectures and practical exercises for skills development
Trainer(s)	Prof Aba Andam; Dr Akosua Darkwah; Prof. Aziato; Dr. Naalamle Amissah
Innovative features	Dedicated sessions to personal skills development of women for advancing their careers, like <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Presentation/public speaking techniques, • Proposal writing skills, • Scientific writing/publishing, • Mediation/negotiation strategies.
Relevance for GE Academy	Innovative methodologies for personal skills development focus
Links to relevant resources	Training website + trainers' slides

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7.7 Factsheet

Name of the training	Gender Strategy
Reference	GR2, Annex A
Promoting institution	University of Western Australia; Oxford University, UK; Durham University, UK
Implementing institution	DR JENNIFER DE VRIES Organisational Consultant Gender Researcher & Strategist
Language of teaching	English
Objective and topic of the training and main priority covered	Priority: Structural change process The workshops aim at supporting university managers and HR staff in the difficult task of moving organisations forward tackling gender inequality and the continuing under-representation of women in leadership.
Country and area of implementation	Australia and UK
Duration of the training	Half day/ 1-day workshop
Period	Not specified
Beneficiaries	HR staff and Middle and top-level managers

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Format	Face-to-face introductory training
Methodology used	<p>De Vries' work is underpinned by what she terms the 'bifocal approach': linking individual development and organisational change. She maintains a strong focus on building the capacity of individuals to understand gender processes and inequalities and develop their capacity to build and lead more gender equitable organisations.</p> <p>Approaches used:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Qualitative and quantitative data driven approach; • Collaborative capacity building approach; • Broad consultation with stakeholders and including management/executive; • Deliberate inclusion of men; • Focus on understanding how gender inequality is produced in the organisation and strategies to address this; • Recommendations framed and designed to ensure they address organisational change processes.
Trainer(s)	Dr Jennifer de Vries and Tim Muirhead
Innovative features	-Use of a F/M couple during trainings (In "Partners for Change" type of training). Working in a female/male facilitator team opens up the territory allowing deeper exploration of the ways in which both women and men contribute to gender inequality and can be part of the solution.
Relevance for GE Academy	See 'Innovative feature'
Links to relevant resources	Jennifer de Vries website

7.8 Factsheet

Name of the training	Developing Female Leaders
Reference	GR20, Annex A
Promoting institution	University of Bath
Implementing institution	Mosaic®
Language of teaching	English
Objective and topic of the training and main priority covered	<p>Priority: ERA: Gender in Decision Making processes and bodies</p> <p>The session includes a presentation of On the Agenda’s recent research on women in European business schools and facilitation of group work to help the participants relate the research to their own individual context and experience. Mosaic® inclusive leadership game would serve as the basis for the group work. The serious game confronts leaders and managers with practical dilemmas that require solutions. A scalable training method that any trained facilitator can use, Mosaic® draws on the players’ own experiences and stimulates problem-solving by creating a safe environment for sharing even the wildest ideas. The outcome is a more flexible, open and inclusive management group that will ultimately benefit the organisation’s efficiency and performance.</p>
Country and area of implementation	Bath, UK

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Duration of the training	Three hours
Period	23 May 2016
Beneficiaries	<p>First session: University's senior female faculty</p> <p>Second session: senior female managers from different private and public organisations</p>
Format	Workshop
Methodology used	<p>30-minute presentation of research on the gender gap in business schools; then 2½ -hour Mosaic® facilitation: the participants are divided into groups of 5. Each group with its own game set. They play 3 rounds simultaneously using 3 of the game's pre-printed dilemmas selected by On the Agenda to facilitate reflection on the main points of the 30-minute presentation. After each round each group is asked to share the highlights of its discussion of the selected dilemma and share their responses to different elements of the game.</p>
Trainer(s)	Dr. Lynn Roseberry
Innovative features	Gamified approach
Relevance for GE Academy	See 'Innovative feature'
Links to relevant resources	<p>Bath University case</p> <p>Serious game description</p>

7.9 Factsheet

Name of the training	Plan of deans/managers/mentors and researchers training - STAGES project
Reference	GR39, Annex A
Promoting institution	STAGES consortium
Implementing institution	Radboud University of Nijmegen: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Donders Institute • Nijmegen School of Management
Language of teaching	Dutch (probably)
Objective and topic of the training and main priority covered	<p>Priority: All</p> <p>Objectives of the training:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -increasing participants' advising and supervising skills regarding gender issues; -increasing participants' knowledge on the effects of gender quota and gender policies; - increasing participants understanding on how to integrate a gender dimension in their research programmes. <p>Topic of the different sessions:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Awareness training on the effects of gender policies and quota; -Training on mentoring skills with respect to (young) female academics; -Training for preparation of a coherent research project on gender issues; -Training on including a gender dimension in the research program.
Country and area of implementation	The Netherlands

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Duration of the training	Four years (12 short sessions)
Period	June 2012 - May 2015
Beneficiaries	Deans, Managers, Mentors and Researchers of Donders Institute for Brain, Cognition and Behavior, and Nijmegen School of Management
Format	Workshop/ in-depth
Methodology used	For the training of the deans and managers and of the researchers, the format of Group Model Building was used. In a series of meetings a causal model was developed of the dynamic changes regarding gender equality within the institution (meeting 1) and the consequences of policies will be discussed (meeting 2). For the training of the researchers, the format of Group Model Building was used as well. In a series of two or more meetings, a facilitator supported the group of researchers in building a causal model on the inclusion of a gender focus in the particular research field. For the training of the mentors, the format of a focus group was used. A facilitator guided the mentors through a group discussion of the merits and pitfalls of mentoring female academics. (Group Model Building as an innovative methodology)
Trainer(s)	Not specified
Innovative features	-Duration of the training -use of the Group Model Building method
Relevance for GE Academy	See 'Innovative features'

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Links to relevant resources	Plan details
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7.10 Factsheet

Name of the training	Analysis of gender inclusion in research
Reference	GR8, Annex A
Promoting institution	UCM (Universidad Complutense Madrid)
Implementing institution	UCM (Universidad Complutense Madrid)
Language of teaching	Spanish
Objective and topic of the training and main priority covered	<p>Priority: ERA: Gender in Research Content</p> <p>The course aims at providing academic staff with the knowledge and skills to include sex/ gender analysis in their research, as part of their official professional development programme.</p> <p>Objectives:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Improve the competencies of the academic staff in the inclusion of the gender perspective both in the research projects and in the scientific articles that may derive from these investigations; - Know the conceptual framework that supports the inclusion of the gender perspective in research and introduce the gender perspective in each of the phases of the research process, from the choice of the research question and the selection of the sample, to the analysis of the results and their subsequent publication; - Analyse the main gender biases of conventional research and the effects on its quality;

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	- Review the relevance of introducing the gender approach in various fields of research with concrete examples of what gender analysis implies in them.
Country and area of implementation	Spain
Duration of the training	5 hours f2f + 15 hours online
Period	From the 10th of January 2019
Beneficiaries	Academic staff
Format	Blended training
Methodology used	It consists of a general presentation of the subject and the course (face-to-face), 4 units (two general and two specific) and a final evaluation (one unit per week + 2 weeks for evaluation). It is a course in blended mode supervised by an expert in the field. The contents are supported by practical examples that help reflection and propose a series of varied and dynamic activities.
Trainer(s)	Capitolina Díaz Martínez
Innovative features	- Blended methodology -At the end of the course and for the evaluation, trainees have to deliver a 4 pages work following a provided template and apply a gender dimension to one of their research projects .
Relevance for GE Academy	See 'Innovative features'

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Links to relevant resources	Web page of the course
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8. Conclusions

In this final chapter, we draw some concluding notes underlining how findings from this study relate to the upcoming design phase of the GE Academy capacity building programme.

8.1 Overall positioning of the GE Academy in the Gender in Research training landscape

In the last 10 years there has been an increasing offer of capacity building/trainings in gender in research, especially enhanced and in most cases made possible by EU funded projects on Structural Change for Gender Equality. As of today, it is not clear yet whether such Topic will be continued under the new programming period and Horizon Europe in particular, also considering the still uncertain future of Swafs (Science with and for Society) overall. Based on knowledge and experience from the consortium, a high demand it is expected towards the GE Academy offer, and this makes it even more likely.

The mapping exercise offers some further hints to be considered and discussed in view of the next project's steps.

- A substantial geographic cleavage is appearing from our map and shows how Central and Eastern European countries have been less poorly covered by gender in research training programmes and activities until now: GE Academy could aim at prioritize those areas when selecting hosting institutions in case demand shall surpass the foreseen offer. Demand from the three most covered countries (ES, IT, DE) could be addressed by facilitating matching and networking with the available gender expertise created via the multiple already developed or still ongoing structural change projects.
- Availability from RPOs in investing own resources on gender trainings is difficult to quantify but doesn't appear to be meaningful as trainings whose costs are supported by RPOs own budgets represent a minor part of the training activities collected in our Database. This topic will be studied more in depth, in view of building the sustainability scenarios for the Pan European Network of Trainers.
- Several of our consulted experts and trainers have recalled the limits of one-off trainings and have stressed how impact can be expected when training is part of a broader change strategy; the risk that the management of Higher Education and RPOs makes use of (one off) gender training as a 'token' for commitment towards structural change or as a 'one fix all' solution, is recalled by previous studies on training in gender mainstreaming (EIGE 2013; QUING/Opera, 2011). It is also a matter of fact that half/one day introductory trainings appear to be the most frequently used format: even though it was not possible to fully track the use of multiple formats by the same institution, short one-off sessions are charged with ambitious goals of addressing complex issues such as gender inequalities in research. When issuing public calls for hosting institutions, criteria for assessing institutional commitment to maximize training impact beyond the one-time individual session could be set.

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- The most covered ERA priority is “Gender in Research Content”, with an over representation of disciplines such as Health and Medicine, and Urban/Transport Studies, and underrepresented ones, IT among them. Instead, there is a reduced share of trainings about other ERA priorities, particularly on “Gender in decision making processes and bodies”. This reflects findings from the ERA Reports on GEPs policies in Research Organizations considering “Gender in Decision Making” as the most poorly addressed area, clearly targeting existing (gendered) power structures in academia and research, and potentially raising more resistances. On the other hand, the state of play for trainings on gender in research content which have been offered quite extensively across Europe, doesn’t reflect the estimated lack of concrete measures taken by RPOs/RFOs as far as the same ERA priority is concerned. Therefore, the GE Academy offer under these 2 priorities should be carefully designed and executed in terms of choice of beneficiaries, formats and contents.

8.2 Design related suggestions for impactful and innovative formats and methodologies

From the several inputs received, mostly from experts, a call for **customization- contextualization of gender in research trainings** was emerging as a shared issue and framed **as an impact driver for change**. An interesting and open question is to what extent customization of training concepts/scripts can play a role in counteracting tokenism in the adoption of one of gender trainings as referred above. Continuous (ex-ante/ex post) and transformative **evaluation** was suggested as a useful tool to this respect. The GE Academy capacity building programme will execute structured formats and training scripts across the EU and is adopting a complex set of standards as a reference/guide to achieve quality. Still, room for customization could be foreseen and some **flexibility** allowed to national trainers for adapting the formats/scripts. A possibility to be taken into consideration includes leaving some slots open for presentations or seminars with knowledgeable representatives with proven expertise from either the hosting organization itself or other relevant local stakeholders. This approach would need to address issues related to autonomy of GE trainers and, eventually, resources.

As already mentioned, emphasis was given to the identification of innovative methods and formats when conducting the mapping of the state of play exercise. This is made even more important in the present scenario featured by the so called “gender fatigue”: this is an ideological dilemma where organizations tend to be represented themselves as internally equal and meritocratic, and their members struggle to acknowledge structural gender inequalities (Kelan, 2009). This appears to be further emphasized after a few decades of (often EC driven) gender equality policies and in the frame of a current general backlash in Europe as far as gender equality is concerned (European Parliament, 2018). Hence, the need for finding new and/or innovative ways to plan, design, execute gender training is made even stronger.

The following relevant aspects have emerged from the study, as far as innovative methodologies are concerned.

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-Innovating with participatory methods. In general, interactivity has become an embedded feature of gender trainings, although it has to be noticed that when asking to experts/projects' representatives for suggesting good practices of gender in research trainings, we still received several conferences as examples. Participatory approaches are usually considered as core elements to distinguish lecturing from capacity building and training, although they are subject to more or less 'radical' interpretations. To this regard, efforts can be made to adapt content and techniques to different working environments and to specific experience and tasks of participants. An even more innovative approach to participatory method consists of 'flipping'/inverting the 'traditional' script which foresees an initial transfer of contents via a presentation from the trainer, to be followed by interactive sessions or working groups. This would imply a more inductive approach, where the training session starts with active engagement of participants and the trainers frame the emerging issues at a later stage only. The creation of multimedia products by participants as part of assignments within workshops or series of trainings can also be considered among highly participatory methodologies. These suggestions apply to face to face formats mostly but are also relevant for the interactive and distributed DOCCs offer which is planned in GE Academy (see below).

-Innovating with technologies. It is quite common to associate innovativeness with the tech component, although it is important not to end up with reductionist views, as the online dimension alone does not represent a guarantee of innovative features by itself. Webinars are typically used for transferring information and knowledge, with limited feedback and interaction taking place within Q&A sessions only. Reflexivity and interactivity in webinars can and should be further enhanced, for example via polling tools to ask for immediate feedback to participants after having shown thought-provoking multimedia materials. This would allow to avoid discontinued attention which is also a risk during webinars. DOCCs experience, although not delivered in a capacity building framework, suggests to make use of a blended, connectivist approach to MOOCs, maximizing interactive learning among participants and trainers via social media. The distributed-decentralized DOCCs approach features multiple face to face classes which can be joined and are complemented by online recorded sessions and assignments.

-Innovating with new trends. Gamified methods and theatre use appear to be new trends to be looked at with attention as inspiring practices. The use of 'serious games' within training sessions can create a 'safer' space apt to tackle sensitive issues such as gender inequalities, where participants can express themselves more freely. Furthermore, a playful touch to training allows creativity and generation of ideas for solutions, overall positively contributing to learning outcomes. An issue to be considered is that in some cases games are sold together with consultancy/training services only. Theatre is bringing participatory, creative and gamified approaches in one, merging the positive elements from all approaches and can also be interpreted through the lenses of feminist pedagogies (see below). Still, it would imply a long duration for the training itself, not always suitable for trainings to be delivered in fast-paced working environments where participants have usually limited time to dedicate. In the GE Academy offer, it could be considered as an option for summer schools only, still implying issues to be addressed in terms of the needed skills from the side of trainers. Rather than envisaging a use of drama methodologies in gender in research capacity building activities, these could inspire the adoption of similar, easier and faster techniques such as "role play", "skits" etc.

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-Innovating through feminist pedagogies. Making use of feminist pedagogies implies multiple attempts: methodologically speaking, it would mean to go beyond an exclusively rational- cognitive approach to learning, adopting techniques which engage participants' body dynamics and emotions. To this regard, engaging people on 'personal' and intimate issues within trainings that are geared towards professional members of academic communities might prove to be challenging although, if properly addressed, it could add value and foster learning and change-related outcomes.

In terms of defining contents and choosing theoretical frameworks for the trainings, feminist pedagogies recall to the importance of keeping the focus on how gender inequalities are linked to broader power imbalances and privileges in society and the economy and to (gender and intersectional) hierarchies in scientific knowledge production (feminist epistemologies). These approaches are challenging more mainstream views of gender equality as resource to achieve excellence in research and compete within the existing socio-economic system: ideological tensions would be added to the training sessions, which could be productive in terms of triggering both engagement and learning.

-Innovating with intersectionality. Addressing the complexities of intersectionality is important to innovate the typical oversimplified and binary vision of gender which is often conveyed during trainings. This might imply to consider the needed additional time to be dedicated to specific aspects and the challenges of operationalizing intersectionality in gender equality policies applied to research institutions. It has to be considered how the adoption of an intersectional approach in trainings might be welcomed or more easily understood in national contexts where a shift to equality for all/diversity policies have been pursued. On the opposite, it could be faced with oppositions and tensions in those countries where regressive social, political and religious movements are increasingly opposing to (intersectional) gender equality and a supposed 'gender ideology' accused to subvert 'traditional' heterosexual and patriarchal family models. Trainers should therefore be equipped for facing and facilitating discussions and resistances which could emerge.

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10. Annexes

10.1 Annex a) Gender in Research Training Map

<https://drive.google.com/open?id=118KbWfleXuiYLC53IRaiwYNtENbz2v0n>

10.2 Annex b) Gender Training Map

<https://drive.google.com/open?id=1SJs2OxuvS0Ay6KnHyQQ-FmoCnOu1sXnE>

10.3 Annex c) Experts' interview grid

<https://drive.google.com/open?id=1RaPs9CI5f36LunT4f3-cX4DeGJEUek-C>